

REPORT ON THE FUNCTIONAL AND NUTRITIONAL PROPERTIES OF THE VALIDATED FOODLAND NEW FOOD PRODUCTS

D5.16

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Short Description
This deliverable reports the results obtained from the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients and food products that have been validated at industrial level following the analytical procedures and methods set up by each partner (D5.15). The functional and nutritional properties have been assessed as final step of the process conducted in all six target countries, considering the definition of the analytical methods, procedures, techniques, tools, and target properties (protocols, D5.15), the conduction of in lab tests (D4.12), and the scientific and technological description of the validated processes for the realization of the new foods (D5.11, D5.14).

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1. Introduction

FoodLAND aims at contributing to the reduction of malnutrition through developing, implementing and validating innovative and sustainable technologies enhancing the nutrition performance of local food systems in Africa. Therefore, the main focus of FOODLAND is to impact on strengthening the African farming and agri-food system through the development of locally-rooted, innovative approaches based on the empowerment of operators along the entire agri-food chain, especially smallholder farmers, which can ultimately lead to the creation of new market opportunities.

Using consumer surveys, FoodLAND assessed food consumption at both individual and household levels that provide a good measure of diet quality and household dietary diversity score in the five African countries that are participating in the project. The data were gathered in the deliverable 2.5. Furthermore, a dataset with the chemico-physical characteristics of relevant (novel and local) food raw materials, ingredients and food products currently entering into the local consumers' diets in the target areas was obtained through a bibliography review.

During the development of the activities in WP2, nutritional recommendations were generated for each FoodLAND country, inclusive of backdrops that provide enhanced understanding of the context of the nutritional issues and possible pathways to their exploitation. These recommendations were the starting step for the research, design and implementation of novel raw materials, food ingredients and food products that aimed to fill the nutritional gaps identified in D2.5 and to realize the nutritional recommendations reported in D2.6.

Based on this initial information, FOODLAND has developed and implemented pilot innovation actions in the network of 14 local Food Hubs paired with African cities, resulting in 26 validated prototypes that will provide African and European consumers with 4 novel raw materials, 10 novel ingredients and 12 novel food products contributing to the nutritional quality of their diets. These are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of the project new food raw materials, ingredients, and products.

(Prototype n.) New project foods	Partner
Raw materials	
(7a, 7b, 8a, 8b) <u>Improved legume lines</u> (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> L.)	SUA
Ingredients	
(11.-14.) <u>Composite flours with new local varieties</u> (<i>vegetables, legumes, cereals</i>) (ST4.4.2)	
11.a wheat; legumes (<i>pea, faba bean, chickpea</i>)	ISACM
11.b vegetables composite flours (<i>leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion</i>)	ISACM
11.c composite flour (<i>white maize, millet, bio-fortified common beans, soybeans, and sesame seeds</i>)	SUA
12. composite flour (<i>orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, biofortified beans</i>)	MAK
13. composite flour: moringa and teff	UoM
14. therapeutic powder for diabetic people (<i>tree tomato</i>) (ST4.5.2)	UoN
15. <u>Dried products</u>	
15.a dried fish (salted, smoked, fermented) from new aquaculture species (<i>Barbus altianalis / Labeo victorianus</i>) (<i>dried, salted and smoked Tilapia, Catfish and Barbus; fermentation for by-products, production of feed</i>)	NARO
15.b dried fish (<i>mullet, tilapia and eel, bottarga</i>)	INAT
15.c dried vegetables (<i>tomato, peppers, strawberries, eggplant, aromatic plants: onion, garlic</i>)	INAT
16. <u>Fish powders</u>	NARO
Food products	
(17.-19.) <u>Oils from new local varieties / species</u>	
17. virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil	ENAM
18. fish oils	NARO

(20.-23.) <u>Snacks from new local varieties / species</u> (ST4.5.3)	
20. orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, biofortified beans	MAK
21.a cookies: wheat; legumes (<i>pea / faba bean / chickpea</i>)	ISACM
21.b energetic bars: wheat flasks; dried fruits (<i>apricot, peach, melon</i>)	ISACM
22. fish cakes and crackers	NARO
23. cereal-based snack for children (<i>quinoa snack for children</i>)	UoN
24. <u>Therapeutic food</u> (<i>tamarillo juice, for adults with diabetes</i>)	UoN
25. <u>Other products</u>	
25.a fish fillets, balls, noodles, nuggets, sausages, and burgers	NARO
25.b bean sauce	NUT
25.c amaranth-enriched wheat	NUT
25.d noodles from orange fleshed sweet potatoes and bio-fortified beans (partially substituting wheat)	MAK

In WP4, the state of the art related to the analytical characterization of selected African traditional and emerging raw materials, ingredients and food products, with a focus on the composition, sensory and nutritional characteristics was analysed and summarized in D4.13. The report also described the first results obtained for the characterization of the functional and nutritional properties of the FoodLAND novel raw materials, ingredients and food products tested at lab-scale.

The objective of Task 5.6 was to carry out the characterization of the new raw materials, ingredients and food products developed by the project and validated at industrial level, to assess their compositions, acceptability and, ultimately, their capacity to ensure balanced and healthy diets. Analytical procedures for characterizing the new products under development, were detailed in D 5.15.

For reasons of confidentiality, to allow partners of the consortium the possibility of publishing the results as original in scientific journal, in this deliverable some of the data have been crypted. The full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI] where an embargo of 6 months is expected (The duration of the embargo could be reviewed/shortened).

2. Results obtained for the characterization of the functional and nutritional properties of the FoodLAND new raw materials, ingredients and food products

2.1. SUA

2.1.1. Raw materials: new improved legume lines (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) (prototype n. 7a, 7b, 8a, 8b)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The new improved legume lines used in this work are Common beans belonging to *Phaseolus vulgaris* L species. Common bean is a vital legume crop, widely valued for its rich nutritional profile, making it an important staple food in many parts of the world (Hummel et al., 2018). The consumption of common bean in developing countries is reported to be higher compared to developed countries due to its readily availability to most people in comparison to meats and fish which are relatively costly to the majority (Beebe et al., 2020). In sub-Saharan Africa, common bean meets more than 50% of the dietary protein requirements; while in East Africa, it is a major staple, the second source of dietary protein, and the third most important source of calories after maize and cassava. Common beans are a valuable source of protein, vitamins, and minerals such as calcium, potassium, phosphorus, iron, copper, zinc, and magnesium. The main objective of this work was to select for bean lines that combine high zinc & iron concentration, acceptable agronomic traits (yield, short maturity time), and short cooking time, while.

To achieve this objective, a set of 90 bean lines were evaluated in the field in research station to start with, where 30 bean lines that performed well in terms of agronomic traits and levels of Fe and Zn were selected for evaluations both in research station and in farmers' fields. Evaluations and selections were continued for several rounds until four best bean lines were identified (16TZMBYPIC-130-1, Mashamba-PYT-4, NUA 660, and NUA 629) that have good levels of Fe and Zn concentration, high yield and short cooking time as compared to the check (Lyamungo 90, normal bean line). These lines are candidates for official release to be used by farmers. These lines have also been analysed/characterized for other nutritional traits.

2. Results

The nutritional properties of the newly improved bean lines are presented in Table 2.1.1.1. It was observed that the bean line NUA-629 exhibited significantly higher levels of both iron and zinc,

with concentrations of 131.3 mg/kg and 29.7 mg/kg, respectively. These values were notably higher compared to the normal common bean as well as the other new improved bean lines. Additionally, NUA-629 demonstrated a substantially higher phosphorus content of 2782.46 mg/kg, surpassing that of the normal common bean (control) and the other three new improved lines. Furthermore, the functional properties of the new improved legume lines are detailed in Table 2.1.1.2. The results of the cooking time (for both soaked and unsoaked beans) for four improved bean lines indicated a reduction in cooking time when the beans were soaked compared to unsoaked. Among these, Mashamba-PYT-4 exhibited the lowest cooking times, with soaked beans cooking in 34 minutes and unsoaked beans in 82 minutes. On the other hand, NUA-629 required the longest cooking time for unsoaked beans among the new lines, suggesting that while it may offer nutritional benefits, it may also demand more time for cooking compared to the others.

Table 2.1.1.1. Main nutritional properties of new improved legume lines

Sample	Protein (g/100g)	Fiber (g/100g)	Calcium (mg)	Iron (mg/kg)	Magnesium (mg)	Potassium (mg)	Sodium (mg)	Zinc (mg/kg)
Lyamungo 90 (check)	21.3	*	*	119.7	*	*	*	28.7
16TZMBYPIC-130-1	21.4	*	*	103.8	*	*	*	28.6
Mashamba-PYT-4	20.3	*	*	125.6	*	*	*	26.8
NUA-629	19.0	*	*	131.3	*	*	*	29.7
NUA-660	20.4	*	*	99.8	*	*	*	25.9

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.1.1.1. Functional properties of the new improved legume lines

Sample	Cooking time (Soaked) (minutes)	Cooking time (Unsoaked) (minutes)
Lyamungo 90 (check)	34	123
16TZMBYPIC-130-1	37	89
Mashamba-PYT-4	34	82
NUA-660	63	103
NUA-629	57	100

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, the newly improved bean lines demonstrate significantly higher concentrations of essential nutrients compared to the normal common beans. These improvements in nutritional content, including higher levels of iron, zinc, and phosphorus, are crucial for addressing nutritional

deficiencies in the population, as identified in D2.6. Furthermore, many of the improved lines exhibit reduced cooking times, which is an important factor for the practical acceptance of beans, particularly in rural areas where cooking time can be a significant barrier to adoption. The reduced cooking time not only enhances convenience but also contributes to increased energy efficiency, benefiting households with limited resources.

The introduction of these new bean lines holds great potential for improving both the nutritional status and the overall well-being of communities, particularly within Food Hubs and across the country. However, before being placed on the market, further characterization regarding the content of anti-nutrient compounds should be carried out. By providing more nutritious and time-efficient beans, these improved lines can play a key role in alleviating micronutrient deficiencies and consistency with the developed nutritional recommendations that aimed to improve healthy diets of the community. Therefore, the widespread adoption of these improved bean lines could have lasting positive effects on public health and contribute to the development of more sustainable and resilient food systems.

4. References

- Beebe, S. (2020). Biofortification of common bean for higher iron concentration. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4, 573449.
- Hummel, M., Hallahan, B. F., Brychkova, G., Ramirez-Villegas, J., Guwela, V., Chataika, B., & Spillane, C. (2018). Reduction in nutritional quality and growing area suitability of common bean under climate change induced drought stress in Africa. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 16187.

2.1.2. Composite flours with new local varieties: composite flour (prototype n. 11c)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Composite flour made from a blend of white maize, millets, soybeans, biofortified common beans, and sesame aims to address the prevalent malnutrition and micronutrient deficiencies in children, particularly in Mvomero Food Hub Morogoro, Tanzania.

The first stage involved selecting local raw materials for the production of composite flours. The materials chosen were white maize, millet, soybeans, biofortified common beans, sesame seeds, and sugar, each selected for its specific nutritional benefits.

Four formulations were selected for testing based on locally available food ingredients and the WHO/UNICEF guidelines for total energy and protein content. In this study the Nutrisurvey software (2007) was used to generate the corresponding proportions of white maize, millets, soybeans, biofortified beans and sesame seeds in composite flour formulations and nutrient optimization. The nutrients optimised were protein, fat, fiber, zinc, iron, calcium, and vitamins A.

The four blends were formulated in triplicates as shown in Table 2.1.2.1. Note: Three 3% sugar was included to enhance the flavor of the final products.

Table 2.1.2.1. Ingredients and formulation for composite flour

Formulation	White maize (%)	Millet (%)	Soybean (%)	Biofortified common beans (%)	Sesame seeds (%)	Sugar for taste (%)
1	60	10	10	15	5	3
2	50	15	10	20	5	3
3	52	10	10	25	3	3
4	53	5	7	30	5	3

For each formulation, two types of composite flour were produced: extruded and non-extruded. For the proximate analysis, moisture content, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, and ash content were determined. In the sensory evaluation, porridge was prepared from each flour formulation and provided to mothers or caregivers for assessment. For the micronutrient analysis, several minerals, including iron and zinc, were measured. In addition, physicochemical properties such as water absorption index, water solubility index, oil absorption index, bulk density, and angle of repose were evaluated.

2. Results

The results of proximate analysis of two composite flour produced are presented in Table 2.1.2.3. The parameter analysed include moisture content, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat and ash content. Extrusion promoted a significant reduction of moisture, protein, fiber and ash content, while fat content was increased.

Table 2.1.2.3. Proximate analysis results for composite flour

S/N	Sample	Moisture content (%)	Crude protein (%)	Crude fiber (%)	Crude fat (%)	Ash content (%)
1	Non-extruded composite flour	*	15.22 ± 1.01 ^a	*	*	*
2	Extruded composite flour	*	12.9 ± 0.71 ^b	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The physico-chemical properties of the composite flours (Table 2.1.2.4) were significantly affected by the extrusion process, that resulted in a higher ability to absorb water (WAI) and solubility (WSI) and a lower ability to absorb oil (OAI). Density and angle of repose were also decreased

after extrusion. On the other side, micronutrients and mineral content (Table 2.1.2.5) was not affected, with the exception of β -carotenoids that were found higher in extruded composite flours.

Table 2.1.2.4. Physico-chemical properties of composite flour

S/N	Sample	Water absorption index 'WAI'	Water solubility index 'WSI'	Oil absorption index 'OAI'	Bulk density, g/cm ³	Angle of Repose
1	Non-extruded composite flour	*	*	*	*	*
2	Extruded composite flour	*	*	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.1.2.5. Micronutrients and vitamin contents of composite flour

Minerals contents mg/kg, except K is in %										
Product	β carotenoids $\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g}$	Total phenol mg/100 g	Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn	Ca	Mg	K %	Na
Non-extruded composite flour	*	*	*	41.42 \pm 0.38 ^a	165.9 \pm 9 \pm 0.01 ^a	*	*	*	*	*
Extruded composite flour	*	*	*	42.59 \pm 0.82 ^a	198.5 \pm 1 \pm 1.81 ^a	*	*	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

On the basis of the observation that Uganda faces co-existence of under nutrition, nutritional deficiency and over nutrition (as reported in D25), food products high in micro and macro nutrients as well as foods high in phytochemicals are needed, to specially target persons at risk of under nutrition. The developed noodles are aligned with this need since they are high in protein, fibre and micro nutrients. These therefore have the potential to contribute to alleviation of micro nutrient deficiency and non-communicable diseases associated with over nutrition. The noodles therefore can contribute to addressing the nutritional recommendations developed for Uganda under the FoodLAND project (D2.6). Sensory evaluation scores for the noodles were relatively high. This reveals high potential for market acceptance of the product. If commercialized and widely consumed, this product would contribute to addressing the key nutrition problems Uganda faces and create demand for the crops, hence contributing to creating market for farm produce.

Finally, it is important to underline that a full aminoacid profile should be carried out, to verify the content of all the essential aminoacids, and mycotoxin analysis of cereals should be carried out for safety aspects.

2.2. ISACM

2.2.1. Composite flours with new local varieties: wheat, faba bean and pea (prototype n. 11a)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The composite flour is composed of 80% of wheat, 10% of faba bean and 10% of green pea, raw materials were obtained from the food hub Chebika/Enfidha at dried form. Raw materials were grinded using a 12 hammer mill (Figure 2.2.1.1) and sieved to obtain homogenous flour. The obtained composite flour was subjected to nutritional and functional analysis compared to control (100% wheat flour). The presented product is suitable for the preparation of soup locally prepared with wheat flour or barley flour.

Figure 2.2.1.1. The milling system used in the validation assay (a) and the new food product wheat and legumes composite flour (b)

2. Results

The obtained results for the new food products physicochemical characterization are presented in the table 2.2.1.1.

Table 2.2.1.1. Physicochemical properties of composite flour (wheat 80%, faba bean (10%) and pea (10%) compared to control (wheat flour)

Parameters	Wheat flour	New food product		P-value
		Composite flour (wheat, faba bean and pea)		
Dry matter (%)	*	*	*	
Protein content (%)	*	*	*	
Total phenols (mg/100g)	57.33±0.56	115.63±7.54		0.000
Antioxidant activity For 100mg of product	DPPH inhibition (%) 77.13±0.31	95.24±1.01		0.000
	Ferric reducing power (absorbance)	*	*	*
Colour parameters				
L*	*	*	*	*
a*	*	*	*	*
b*	*	*	*	*

DPPH: 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The obtained results showed significant differences for all the studied parameters between the new product and the control. An enhancement of the nutritional and nutraceutical properties is observed with the legume supplementation. Legumes are known as a source of proteins, fibres, vitamins and minerals and phenolic compounds (Duodu, and Minnaar, 2011; Millar et al., 2019). Legume proteins are relatively low in sulphur-containing amino acids, methionine, cysteine and tryptophan, but high in lysine. Therefore, legumes and cereals are nutritionally complementary (Petitot et al., 2010).

The colour characteristics have also been significantly impacted by the legume flour supplementation; this is because legumes, especially green peas, contain pigments like chlorophyll. However, the colour variation is smaller than 5 units for the different parameters which can be acceptable for consumer.

The results of functional properties of the samples (bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner ratio, water absorbance capacity, water solubility index, oil absorption capacity and swelling capacity) are displayed in table 2.2.1.2.

Table 2.2.1.2. Functional properties of composite flour (wheat 80%, faba bean (10%) and pea (10%) compared to control (wheat flour)

Parameters	Wheat flour	New food product	P-value
		Composite flour (wheat, faba bean and pea)	
Bulk density (BD)	521.015±20.84	606.83±15.83	0.000
Tapped density (TD)	770.71±51.76	840.76±41.90	0.047
Compressibility index (CI)	*	*	*
Hausner ratio (HR)	*	*	*
Water Absorption Capacity (WAC) (g/g)	*	*	*
Water Solubility Index (WSI) (%)	*	*	*
Oil Absorption Capacity (OAC) (g/g)	*	*	*
Swelling index (SI)	*	*	*

Values are presented as means ±SD

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

With the exception of the compressibility index, Hausner ratio, and water absorption capacity, the majority of wheat flour's functional characteristics have been impacted by the addition of legume flours. Duodu, and Minnaar, (2011) indicated that composite doughs of wheat with legumes tend to have higher water absorption and lower strength and stability.

For flour intended to soup preparation, the most important functional properties are water holding capacity (higher water absorption leads to a thicker and more stable consistency), gelatinization (related to starch content) and viscosity (depending on flour solubility and dispersibility). The presented results can confirm that the legume supplementation can maintain or improve the soup rheological properties.

3. Conclusions

According to D2.5, a decline of wheat consumption has been observed for Tunisian consumer diet in conjunction with modernization and westernization of the diet especially in urban areas towards more consumption of dairy and meat products, sugar, fat and salt. However, refined soft wheat remains the most important source of total calories intake. In addition, the consumption of legumes presents a common habit for Mediterranean diet. Therefore, our new product “wheat, legumes composite flour” can easily find its place in the eating habits of the Tunisian consumer. Based on deliverable D2.6, the new food product wheat and legumes (faba bean, pea) composite flour, satisfies nutritional the presented guidelines for Tunisian consumers who are suffering from problems of deficiencies, in particular, anemia in pregnant women and children, underweight in preschool children as well as certain deficiencies in nutrients or vitamins. The new product can provide a well-balanced profile of macronutrients and micronutrients that are appropriate for making soup. In addition to using faba bean and pea flours, which are strong in plant-based protein, dietary fiber, and vital minerals like iron and magnesium, the recipe makes use of wheat’s high carbohydrate content for energy. The new product can also fulfill important dietary requirements including better protein quality and less glycemic response, this synergy raises the nutritional value. Additionally, by satisfying the dietary requirements for fiber consumption, fostering gut health, and providing a gluten-inclusive substitute that is still appropriate for a variety of culinary uses, the composite flour is intended to enhance dietary consistency.

In addition, the new product can be adequate for the different intended beneficiaries of the nutritional recommendations: Children, Women in Reproductive Age (WRA), Rural consumers and Urban consumers.

Finally, it is important to underline the need for mycotoxin analysis in cereals as critical aspect to ensure food safety.

4. References

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2.2.2. Vegetables composite flour (leaf: parsley, spinach, chard; bulb: potato, carrot; spice: tomato, onion) (prototype n. 11b)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The vegetables spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*), chard (*Beta vulgaris*), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), carrot (*Daucus carota*), potato (*Solanum tuberosum*), tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) (Dorra variety) and white onion (*Allium cepa*) (Figure 2.2.2.1) were collected from different farmers in the food hub Enfidha/Chebika. All vegetables were washed dried in the convective dryer and grinded using a 12 hammer mill (figure 2.2.1.1) and sieved at a particle size $\phi < 0.5\text{mm}$ Figure 2.2.2.3 to be used for further analysis.

Figure 2.2.2.1. Vegetables used for composite flour formulation: chard (a, h), spinach (b, i),

parsley (c, j), potato (d, k), carrot (e, l), onion (f, m) and tomato (g, n)

Figure 2.2.2.3. Vegetables composite flour for soup

2. Results

The results of physicochemical properties of the vegetables composed flour are presented in table 2.2.2.1.

Table 2.2.2.1. Physicochemical properties of vegetables composite flour

Parameters		Values
Dry matter (%)		*
Total phenols (mg/100g)		339.75±18.40
Antioxidant activity for 100mg of product	DPPH inhibition (%)	100.00±0.00
	Ferric reducing power (absorbance)	*
Colour parameters		
L*		*
a*		*
b*		*

Values are presented as means ±SD

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Comprising several vegetable flours from leafy vegetables (parsley, spinach, and chard), bulbs (carrot and potato), and spices (onion and tomato), the composite flour exhibits remarkable

nutritional and nutraceutical qualities. In fact, the content of dry matter ($91.67 \pm 2.90\%$) indicates low moisture, improves the flour's shelf stability and qualifies it for convenient soup preparation and long-term preservation.

The flour's abundance of beneficial components is highlighted by its high phenolic content. Its antioxidant potential and health-promoting qualities are further enhanced by the addition of spinach, parsley, chard and tomato, all of which are renowned for their high phenolic content. These vegetables allowed a DPPH Inhibition percentage of 100 % for 100mg of product.

The higher absorbance value for ferric reducing power indicates a good ability of the composite flour for effective electron-donating, further affirming the flour's role in neutralizing oxidative stress. The antioxidant properties of the vegetables are one of the most present label claims due to the high levels of carotenoids, tocopherols and ascorbic acid that have epidemiological evidence of benefiting human health (Santos et al., 2014, Thuy et al., 2024).

This composite flour blends the nutritional richness and functional benefits of various vegetables, offering a convenient, nutrient-dense option for creating flavorful, antioxidant-rich soups. It combines high fiber, vitamins, minerals, and bioactive compounds, making it a valuable addition to a health-focused diet (Damndja et al., 2024).

The moderate lightness (L^* value) of 54.41 ± 1.42 suggests a slightly darker shade, reflecting the natural pigments of leafy greens like spinach and chard. The a^* value (4.05 ± 0.37) indicates a slight red tint which can be attributed to the presence of tomato and carrot, which are rich in carotenoids. The b^* value (22.27 ± 0.46) indicates a pronounced yellow color resulting from the natural pigmentation of carrot, potato, and onion, enhancing the visual appeal of the flour.

The functional properties of properties of the vegetables composed flour are displayed in table 2.2.2.2.

The functional properties of the vegetables composite flour highlight its potential performance in food applications, particularly in soup preparation. The relatively low bulk density ($288.59 \pm 7.62 \text{ kg/m}^3$) suggests that the flour is lightweight, which is beneficial for packaging and storage but might require adjustments before processing to achieve optimal flowability during handling. The significantly higher tapped density (TD: $717.46 \pm 14.02 \text{ kg/m}^3$) compared to the bulk density indicates that the flour particles can be compacted under vibration or tapping, which reflects the powder's potential to minimize air spaces when packed. However, high Compressibility Index ($59.76 \pm 1.28\%$) is observed, suggesting that the flour may clump or bridge during processing and handling, since a CI above 30% indicates poor flowability. High value (>1.4) of Hausner Ratio (HR: 2.49 ± 0.08) further confirms poor flowability. This could be attributed to the fine particle size ($<0.5\text{mm}$) or irregular shape of the flour particles, common in vegetable-derived flours.

Table 2.2.2.2. Functional properties of vegetables composite flour

Parameters	Values
Bulk density (BD)	288.59±7.62
Tapped density (TD)	717.46±14.02
Compressibility index (CI)	*
Hausner ratio (HR)	*
Water Absorption Capacity (WAC) (g/g)	*
Water Solubility Index (WSI) (%)	*
Oil Absorption Capacity (OAC) (g/g)	*
Swelling index (SI)	*

Values are presented as means ±SD

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

On the other side, the high WAC (5.40 ± 0.22 g/g) indicates the flour's excellent ability to bind water, which is advantageous for soup preparation as it can enhance viscosity, texture and mouthfeel. A moderate Water Solubility Index (WSI: $25.625 \pm 0.98\%$): reflects the flour's capacity to release soluble components into water, suggesting that it can contribute to the solubility and dispersion of nutrients in soup formulations.

A notable Oil Absorption Capacity (OAC: 2.83 ± 0.1 g/g) signifies the flour's ability to retain oil, which can improve flavor retention and contribute to the overall richness of soups. Water and oil absorption capacity are considered important parameter in viscous food such as porridge and soup (Tutu et al., 2024). The high swelling index (SI: 7.32 ± 0.53) indicates that the flour can expand significantly in water, contributing to increased volume and a desirable thickening effect in soup.

We can confirm that the vegetables composite flour demonstrates excellent water absorption, swelling, and oil retention capacities, making it well-suited for soups that require a thick, creamy texture and enhanced flavor.

3. Conclusions

According to D 2.5, even though the consumption of fruits and vegetables is increasing in Tunisia, it is still below the WHO recommended level. Vegetables are consumed fresh or processed. The

presence of flour composed of several vegetables can be an opportunity for consumers to benefit from the specific properties of each vegetable at the same time.

Referring to D2.6, the food transition for Tunisian consumer has caused a drop in cereal consumption but has in turn contributes to the increase in consumption of refined soft wheat. This generated a diet not deficient in terms of energy and proteins but deficient in minerals and vitamins. This is why, in addition to the fight against overweight and obesity, Tunisia must also face certain problems of deficiencies, notably anemia in pregnant women and children, underweight in kindergarten children as well as certain nutrient or vitamin deficiencies. The introduction of our new product in the Tunisian consumer diet can promotes health benefits since dried vegetables retain most of their nutrients during the dehydration process, they are rich in vitamins like A, C, K, and some B-complex vitamins, essential for skin health, immunity, and energy production. They also contain minerals like iron (important for women and children prone to anemia), calcium (for bone health), and potassium (for muscle function and blood pressure regulation). High content in dietary fiber, supports healthy digestion, reduces the risk of constipation, and maintains healthy cholesterol levels. Fiber also promotes satiety, helping with weight management. Finally, vegetables antioxidants such as carotenoids, flavonoids, and polyphenols that help combat oxidative stress and reduce the risk of chronic diseases like heart disease and cancer.

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2.2.3. Snacks from new local varieties / species (cookies): wheat; legumes (pea / faba bean / chickpea) (prototype n. 21a)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

For the validation assay, untreated and germinated faba bean were selected for cereal, legumes composite flour based on their interesting chemical composition and nutritional, functional and sensory properties of the cookies. Raw materials were obtained from the food hub Chebika/Enfidha. Three batches of cookies were formulated using 100% wheat flour (control), the second batch: wheat flour (80%) and untreated faba bean flour (20%) and the third batch: wheat flour (80%) and germinated faba bean flour (20%) (Figure 2.2.3.1).

For each batch the same ingredients were added which are: eggs, milk powder, vegetable fat, sugar, salt and baking powder.

Figure 2.2.3.1. Cookies preparation in the “Cherif pastry”, untreated faba bean flour (UFBF), Germinated faba bean flour (GFBF)

2. Results

Colour and textural parameters

The results of colour parameters L^* , a^* and b^* and textural properties (hardness and adhesiveness) are presented in table 2.2.3.1.

Table 2.2.3.1. Colour and textural parameters of cookies

Sample	L*	a*	b*	Hardness (g)	Adhesiveness (g/s)
Control	66.06±3.00 ^a	*	*	1027±150b	*
Cookies UFB	60.45±1.89 ^b	*	*	1150±217b	*
Cookies GFB	66.04±1.71 ^a	*	*	1279±291a	*

UFB: Untreated faba bean; GFB: Germinated Faba bean; values are presented as means ±SD. n=20
^{a,b,c} different letters indicate significant difference within rows

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The colour parameters (L*, a* and b*) showed significant difference between cookies samples the cookies supplemented with germinated faba bean have similar values to the control. The colour change for cookies with untreated faba bean flour can be attributed to its chemical composition which can promote Maillard reaction during baking.

The textural parameters hardness and adhesiveness showed a significant difference between the cookies with highest values in the supplemented faba bean cookies. This result is similar to Chakraborty and Singh (2024) who indicated observed an increase in hardness values in wheat-cowpea flour composite bread.

Physicochemical properties

The physicochemical properties of the cookies are displayed in the table 2.2.3.2. The statistical analysis showed no significant difference for dry matter; however, weight loss, spread ratio (D/T), total phenol content, DPPH radical inhibition percentage and ferric reducing power were significantly different with P values of 0.037 for weight loss and P<0.001 for the other parameters. Faba bean supplementation has improved the nutritional composition and promoted health benefits of cookies. Particularly, the germinated faba bean is more effective. It has been reported that in addition to the reduction of antinutritional compounds, germination also had a positive effect on vitamin content. Indeed, vitamin C (ascorbic acid) was almost 50-fold higher in the germinated seed than the dry seed, while vitamin B2 (riboflavin) increased by 40% after 4 days of germination (Verni, Coda and Rizzello, 2019).

Long-term consumption of secondary metabolites, which are abundant in faba beans, has been identified in recent years as a major factor in the prevention of chronic and incurable diseases including cancer, cardiovascular disease, type II diabetes, etc (Rahate et al., 2020).

Table 2.2.3.2. Physicochemical properties of cookies

Sample	Dry matter (%)	Weight loss (%)	D/T	Ash content (%)	Total phenol content mg/100g DM	DPPH scavenging activity IP (%)	FRAP (absorbance)
Control	90±5.27	*	*	1.07±0.17 ^b	70.00±0.02 ^c	*	*
Cookies UFB	91.5±5.80	*	*	1.35±0.03 ^a	90.00±0.01 ^b	*	*
Cookies GFB	89±6.15	*	*	1.52±0.04 ^a	117.00±0.04 ^a	*	*

UFB: Untreated faba bean; GFB: Germinated faba bean; D/T : Diameter/Thickness; DPPH: DPPH: 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical; FRAP: Ferric reducing activity power values are presented as means ±SD.

^{a,b,c} different letters indicate significant difference within rows

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

A higher spread ratio values were observed for the faba bean supplemented cookies, these results are in agreement with those of Dada et al., (2023) who registered a higher spread ratio values in tiger nut flour and African yam bean supplemented biscuits.

The same observation is recorded for total phenol content and antioxidant activity which were enhanced with faba bean supplementation. Those results are also comparable to Dada et al., (2023) who indicated an improvement of total phenol content and antioxidant activity of biscuits in presence of tiger nut flour and African yam bean.

Sensory properties

The sensory evaluation was conducted with 61 panelists from different ages and categories with a proportion of them who are accustomed to tasting tests. The obtained results showed significant differences in colour, grainy texture, crunchy texture and overall appreciation ($P < 0.05$) (table 2.2.3.3). The sensory profile of the cookies presented in figure 2.2.3.2 indicates that the highest scores were obtained for the cookies supplemented with untreated faba bean, which was the most appreciated sample followed by germinated faba bean cookies. The P values for the different descriptors are presented in table 2.2.3.3.

Colour and texture were the most affected parameters of cookies, in particular, faba bean supplemented cookies registered the highest scores. These results are in agreement with the instrumental measurement results.

The present results are encouraging and the quality of the product has been improved at a supplementation level which didn't affect many physical properties.

Table 2.2.3.3. P-values of the descriptor for cookies sensory properties

Descriptor	P values
Colour	<0.001
Appreciated smell	0.181
Sweet taste	0.146
Salty taste	0.149
Flour taste	0.23
Bitter taste	0.55
Bitter After taste	0.46
Friability	0.63
Grainy texture	<0.001
Crunchy texture	<0.001
Overall appreciation	0.0049

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Dry faba bean seed is used in variety of foods, such as Doubanjiang (spicy fermented bean paste), lamb with faba bean (traditional Dalmatian dish), Maccu (traditional Italian soup), Medamis (stewed beans), Falafel (deep fried cotyledon paste with some vegetables and spices), Bissara (a paste prepared from faba bean cotyledon) and Nabet soup (boiled germinated beans). Moreover, a spicy snack prepared from fried faba bean is popular in several countries like China, Malaysia, Colombia, Peru, Guatemala, Mexico, Gilan (a province in northern Iran) and Thailand. It has been reported that faba bean flour is used in gluten-free cake production and also extruded snacks and spaghetti for the positive repercussions on nutritional value and texture (Rahate et al., 2021).

Figure 2.2.3.2. Descriptive sensory profile of cookies, UFB: Untreated faba bean; GFBC: Germinated faba bean; (*) indicates significant difference ($P < 0.05$)

3. Conclusions

According to D 5.2, despite the regression, cereals are still the staple food in the Tunisian diet, cookies as cereal based snack represent a habitual food for Tunisian consumers particularly for children and urban consumers. The new product wheat, faba bean composite flour based cookies can be appreciated by the Tunisian consumers.

Referring to D 2.6, overweight and obesity, certain problems of deficiencies, notably anemia in pregnant women and children, underweight in kindergarten children as well as certain nutrient or vitamin deficiencies are the most important problems in Tunisia. The introduction of untreated and germinated Faba bean in the children diet can be a good solution to improve their health situation. In fact, snacks are important in today's diets since they provide nourishment in between meals. When thoughtfully selected, snacks can be a beneficial supplement to a person's diet, helping to maintain energy levels, control hunger, and provide vital nutrients. Although they can improve the diet, they can also lead to an excessive consumption of calories if taken improperly, particularly in excess. Because they are made without the use of fat (frying), dried or baked snacks are healthier and may have fewer calories. They are also distinguished by their high fiber content and other dietary components that are beneficial, namely vitamins, minerals, and generally antioxidant-containing substances, all while retaining their sensory qualities (Chobot et al., 2024).

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2.2.4. Snacks from new local varieties / species (energetic bars): wheat flasks; dried fruits (apricot, peach, melon) (prototype n. 21b)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

For the validation process, a formulation including dried fruits (60%), wheat flakes (22%), and glucose syrup (18%) was tested. The fruits used were apricots (Khad Hlima variety), peaches (Boutabgaya variety), and melons (Zehira variety). Wheat flakes were prepared from *Triticum durum* (Maali variety). Fruits and wheat were collected from the Enfidha/Chebika food hub during May and June. The preparation process involved cutting, drying, and grinding the fruits. For the wheat flakes, the grains were cleaned, soaked in water for 12 hours, boiled for 1 hour, then ground, flattened, and baked at 150°C for 1 hour. All the ingredients were then mixed, and submitted to forming, pressing and then cooled at 4 °C. Subsequently, the bars were cut into pieces, packed and stored under refrigeration (4±1 °C) (Figure 2.2.4.1).

Figure 2.2.4.1. Ingredients and preparation of energetic bars based on wheat flakes and dried fruits (apricot, peach and melon)

2. Results

Physical parameters

The results of colour parameters L^* , a^* and b^* and textural properties (hardness) are presented in table 2.2.4.1.

The obtained results are close the results obtained in the lab scale test. The L^* value about 37 suggests a relatively dark color, as the scale ranges from 0 (black) to 100 (white). The positive values of a^* and b^* indicate product redness and yellowness respectively. The combination of moderate brightness (L^*), reddish tones (a^*), and yellowish hues (b^*) suggests a warm, visually

appealing color typical of fruit-based products it also might be related to Maillard and caramelization reactions during food bars preparation (Cavalcanti et al., 2024).

For the texture, a value of 2200 g suggests a relatively firm texture, which is typical for energetic bars designed to hold their shape and provide a satisfying bite. Kowalska et al. (2021) reported that for multigrain bars about 2 cm thick, softness is required and those up to about 1 cm thick can be crunchy.

Table 2.2.4.1. Physical properties of energetic bars

Parameters	Values
L*	36.93±2.34
a*	*
b*	*
Hardness (g_{force})	*

Values are presented as means ±SD.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Physicochemical and nutritional properties

The results of physicochemical and nutritional properties of energetic bars are displayed in table 2.2.4.2.

Table 2.2.4.2. Physicochemical and nutritional properties of energetic bars

Parameters	Values
Water content (%)	*
Ash content (%)	2.37±0.20
pH	*
Acidity (%)	*
Protein content (%)	13.43±2.71
Sugar content (%)	*
Fat content (%)	*
TPC (mg/100g)	*
Antioxidant activity	*
DPPH inhibition (%) for 50mg	*

Values are presented as means ±SD.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The moisture content of the bars falls within an acceptable range for energy bars, ensuring they are neither too dry nor too moist. This balance contributes to a desirable texture and enhances shelf stability (Cavalcanti et al., 2024). With a pH of 3.4, the bars are acidic, which is typical for products containing dried fruits. This acidity not only imparts a tangy flavor but also helps inhibit microbial growth, further extending shelf life. The acidic level is consistent with the inclusion of

fruits like apricots, peaches, and melons, adding a refreshing tang while aiding preservation. The bars contain a moderate protein content, due to the inclusion of wheat flakes, which contain gluten and some plant-based proteins, making them suitable for providing sustained energy and promoting satiety, which is ideal for an energy product. The high sugar content, primarily from the natural sugars in dried fruits, delivers a quick energy boost, aligning with the purpose of energy bars. The low fat content is consistent with the bars' focus on being a fruit-based energy product, making them appealing to health-conscious consumers. Additionally, the bars are rich in phenolic compounds, which are known for their antioxidant properties, underscoring their functional value as a health-promoting snack. The complete DPPH inhibition (100%) indicates exceptional antioxidant activity, likely due to the natural compounds present in the dried fruits. This positions the bars as a functional food with significant health benefits, catering to consumers seeking natural, antioxidant-rich snacks that provide quick energy and sustained satiety. Overall, these bars are well-suited for a health-conscious market, offering a combination of natural ingredients, quick energy, and functional health benefits.

Microbiological properties

The enumeration results of total aerobic mesophilic flora (TAMF), yeasts and molds (Y/M), total and fecal coliforms are presented in table 2.2.4.3.

Table 2.2.4.3. Microbiological properties

Germ (CFU/g)	Values
Total aerobic mesophilic flora (TAMF)	6.910 ³
Yeast and molds Y/M	*
Total coliforms	*
Fecal coliforms	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The Total Aerobic Mesophilic Flora (TAMF) was measured at 6.9 x 10³ CFU/g, which is within acceptable limits for this type of product, indicating that the microbial load is controlled and does not pose a risk to consumer health. The Yeasts and Molds count was reported as <10 CFU/g, which is well below the threshold for spoilage, confirming that the product is free from contamination that could affect its sensory quality. Additionally, both Total Coliforms and Fecal Coliforms were absent, further assuring that the product adheres to strict hygienic standards and is safe for consumption. These microbiological results support the product's safety profile and confirm its compliance with relevant food safety regulations (Budin et al., 2025).

Sensory analysis

The acceptance test results of the energetic bars are shown in table 2.2.4.4.

Table 2.2.4.4. Sensory evaluation of energetic bars

Parameters	Score
Colour	*
Appearance	*
Fruity smell	*
Wheat smell	*
Acid taste	*
Sweet taste	*
Hand consistency	*
Mouth consistency	*
Over all appreciation	6.7±0.82

Values are presented as means ±SD.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The sensory evaluation results provide valuable insights into the acceptability of the energy bars across various attributes:

The colour of the bars received a high score (6.8 ± 0.79), indicating that the visual appeal is well-appreciated, likely due to the natural tones contributed by the dried fruits. Similarly, appearance scored moderately (5.5 ± 0.99), suggesting that while acceptable, there is some room for improvement in visual presentation to enhance consumer appeal further. Regarding aroma, the fruity smell (5.3 ± 1.64) and wheat smell (5.5 ± 1.51) achieved moderate ratings, reflecting that the aroma is recognizable but could be more pronounced to better align with consumer expectations. This could involve optimizing the balance of fruit and cereal aromas during the preparation process.

The flavor profile showed mixed results. The sweet taste (6.2 ± 0.84) was well-received, highlighting that the natural sweetness from dried fruits and glucose meets consumer preferences. However, the acid taste (4.1 ± 1.60) scored lower, suggesting that the acidity may be perceived as too strong by some consumers, potentially overshadowing the overall flavor balance. In terms of texture, both hand consistency (6.6 ± 0.97) and mouth consistency (6.6 ± 0.84) were highly appreciated, indicating that the bars have a satisfying firmness and mouthfeel, essential for a positive sensory experience.

Finally, the overall appreciation (6.7 ± 0.82) demonstrates that the energy bars are generally well-liked by consumers. This high score underscores the product's potential as a nutritionally balanced and sensory-pleasing snack.

3. Conclusions

According to D 5.2, despite the decrease in their consumption, cereals are still the staple food in the Tunisian diet. Even though the consumption of fruits is increasing, it is still below the WHO recommended level in Tunisia. The new product, energetic bars made with wheat flakes and dried fruits, aligns with these dietary habits and is likely to be well-received by the Tunisian population. Referring to D 2.6, Tunisia faces several nutritional challenges, including overweight and obesity, anemia, underweight in kindergarten children, and deficiencies in essential nutrients and vitamins. This highlights the importance of introducing nutritionally balanced products like these energy bars. Designed with a blend of wheat and nutrient-rich dried fruits, they offer a source of essential vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, potentially addressing some of these dietary deficiencies. The introduction of this new product is significant not only for its alignment with traditional eating patterns but also for its potential to contribute to improving public health. By providing a convenient, affordable, and nutrient-dense snack, these energetic bars can support better nutrition for children key vulnerable group in Tunisia, while also promoting healthier snacking habits. Additionally, the production of these bars supports local agriculture, utilizing Tunisian wheat and fruits, thereby encouraging economic sustainability and local development.

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2.3. INAT

2.3.1. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15b), dried vegetables (prototype n. 15c)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Raw fish: More than 30 specimens of each fish species (Tilapia; *Oreochromis niloticus*, and Mullet: *Mugil cephalus*) were caught in the Bouhertma dam, located in the north hydrological watershed of Medjerda during autumn 2024 and directly transferred to the laboratory for biochemical analysis. For mullet, both eggs and fillets were used. Eggplant (*Solanum melongena* L.) and strawberries (*Fragaria x ananassa* Duchesne) were purchased from local market in the Jendouba foodhub.

2. Results

Dried vegetables:

Despite its nutritional interest, strawberry is a highly perishable fruit with intense metabolic activity after harvest. Such fact would make its consumption restricted to short time. Preserving strawberries by drying would enhance their consumption all year long and avoid their spoilage. Strawberries samples were subjected to solar drying directly and to both osmotic dehydration and solar drying. Proximate composition of dried strawberries is summarized in Table 2.3.1.1.

Table 2.3.1.1: Nutritional attributes of dried strawberries

	a_w	Moisture content (%)	Protein (%)	Crude fat (%)	Ash (%)	Potassium (ppm)	Vitamin C (mg/100g)
Dried strawberries	0.564±0.003	*	*	*	*	*	*
Dried strawberry treated with osmotic dehydration	0.540±0.006	*	*	*	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Solar drying led to significant decrease in water activity (a_w), below 0.600 which allows preservation of dried strawberries (Table 2.3.1.1) by inhibiting microbial growth (Fellows, 2009). Interestingly, osmotic dehydration pre-treatment improved vitamin C preservation during drying process, while no significant impact was observed for the other nutritional properties. Vitamin C improves the absorption of non-heme iron, the form of iron present in plant-based foods. In case of eggplant, solar drying led also to a better preservation ($a_w < 0.600$). Osmotic dehydration did not induce significant changes in the nutritional attributes, except for ash content.

Table 2.3.1.2: Nutritional properties of dried eggplant

	a_w	Moisture content (%)	Protein (%)	Crude fat (%)	Ash (%)	Potassium (ppm)
Dried eggplant	0.554±0.009	*	*	*	*	*
Dried eggplant treated with osmotic dehydration	0.539±0.002	*	*	*	*	*

**p<0.01

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Regarding functional properties, rehydration capacity of dried strawberries and eggplant was assessed at 60°C. Osmotic dehydration did not affect this property in dried strawberries as it was the case with eggplant. The difference could be related to the approach used in osmotic dehydration: in the case of strawberries, a solution of sucrose and salt was used, while eggplant slices were covered with dry salt that could occupy some intercellular gaps induced by drying.

Figure 2.3.1.1: Rehydration capacity of dried vegetables

Regarding textural and thermal properties (Table 2.3.1.3), osmotic dehydration pretreatment did not affect hardness of dried vegetables. DSC analysis showed an endothermic peak at 107°C for dried eggplant slices, while no thermal events were detected in the case of strawberries.

Table 2.3.1.3: Textural and thermal properties of dried strawberries and eggplant

	Hardness (N)	Thermal properties (°C)		
		Ti	Tp	Tf
Dried eggplant	9.42±0.38	102.05	107.44	107.85
Dried eggplant treated with osmotic dehydration	*	*	*	*
Dried strawberries	7.87±1.12	ND	ND	ND
Dried strawberry treated with osmotic dehydration	*	*	*	*

Ti: Initial temperature; Tp: Peak temperature; Tf: final temperature; ND: Not detected

** Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]*

Dried fish:

Fish fillet were subjected to salting before drying, mainly to decrease their moisture content. Results showed that this pretreatment affected only the final moisture and ash content for Tilapia, while no significant changes were observed for mullet. Dried fish fillet had a high protein content ranging between 36.16 and 77.89%, which highlights the nutritional interest of their consumption. Previous research reported protein content of sun-dried fish ranging from 49.23–62.85% (Fitri et al., 2022), these averages depend on the type of fish used.

Table 2.3.1.4: Proximate composition of dried fish fillet

Sample	<i>Tilapia</i>				<i>Mullet</i>			
	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)
Salted dried fillet	11.55±0.29*	**	**	4.04±1.09	14.48±0.33	**	**	5.26±0.25
Dried fillet	10.39±0.23*	**	**	5.04±1.36	20.65±3.15	**	**	5.54±0.19

*p<0.05

** Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

A particular focus was dedicated to fatty acids composition. Both species showed a diversity in fatty acids composition, marked by the presence of saturated, monounsaturated and

polyunsaturated ones. Thus, dried fish fillet could be considered a valuable source of nutrients and health promoting compounds (Tenyang et al., 2020).

Table 2.3.1.5: Fatty acids composition of dried fish fillets

Fatty acid	<i>Tilapia</i>		<i>Mullet</i>	
	Salted dried fillets	Dried fillets	Salted dried fillets	Dried fillets
Total	2.98	3.31	2.12	2.06
Butyric acid	*	*	*	*
Caporic acid	*	*	*	*
Capric acid	*	*	*	*
Tridecanoic acid	*	*	*	*
Myristic acid	*	*	*	*
Pentadecanoic acid	*	*	*	*
Palmitic acid	*	*	*	*
Heptadecanoic acid	*	*	*	*
Stearic acid	*	*	*	*
Arachidic acid	*	*	*	*
Tricosanoic acid	*	*	*	*
Heneicosanoic	*	*	*	*
Cis-11-eicosadienic	*	*	*	*
<hr/>				
Total	1.56	1.59	0.84	1.5
Myristoleic acid	*	*	*	*
Palmitoleic acid	*	*	*	*
cis-10 heptadecanoic acid	*	*	*	*
Oleic acid	*	*	*	*
Erucic acid	*	*	*	*
Nervonic acid	*	*	*	*
<hr/>				
Total	0.63	0.71	1.08	1.48
Linoleic acid	*	*	*	*
Gamma linolenic acid	*	*	*	*
Linolenic acid	*	*	*	*
Cis-8-11-14-ecosatrienoic aci	*	*	*	*
Cis-5,8,11,14,17-eicosapentaenoic	*	*	*	*
Cis-4,7,10,13,16,19-docosahexaenoic	*	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Bottarga:

The eggs of the mullets, usually known as roes, are removed from the fish in their original ovarian sac and manufactured through a salting and a drying process (Caredda et al., 2018). After salting, two methods were tested: solar drying and drying at room temperature. Except drying time (shorter with solar drying), drying method did not affect the proximate composition of bottarga (Table 2.3.1.6). Results show a high content in fat and protein content.

Table 2.3.1.6: Proximate composition of dried bottarga

	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Ash (%)	Fat (%)
Solar drying	17.75±1.44	*	*	22.75±0.37
Common drying	20.46±0.46	*	*	23.21±0.06

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Analysis of fatty acids composition (Table 2.3.1.7) showed a high content of unsaturated ones. Introducing bottarga consumption regularly in a diversified diet would be helpful to address nutritional needs and accordingly promote a healthy diet.

Table 2.3.1.7: Fatty acids composition of Bottarga

	Fatty acid	Solar drying	Common drying	
	Total	14.85	15.58	
	Butyric acid	*	*	
	Capric acid	*	*	
	Undecanoic	*	*	
	Tridecanoic	*	*	
	Myristic	*	*	
Saturated fatty acid (%)	Pentadecanoic	*	*	
	Palmitic	*	*	
	Heptadecanoic	*	*	
	Stearic	*	*	
	Arachidic	*	*	
	Heneicosanoic	*	*	
	Cis-11-eicosadienic	*	*	
	Tricosanoic	*	*	
		Total	5.49	5.65
		Myristoleic	*	*
Monounsaturated fatty acids (%)	Palmitoleic	*	*	
	Cis-10 heptadecanoic	*	*	
	Oleic	*	*	
	Cis-11-eicosenoic	*	*	
	Erucic	*	*	

	Nervonic	*	*
Polyunsaturated fatty acids (%)	Total	2.27	1.95
	Linoleic	*	*
	Gamma linolenique	*	*
	Linolenic	*	*
	Cis-8-11-14-ecosatrienoic	*	*
	Cis 11-14-17-ecosatrienoic	*	*
	Cis-5,8,11,14,17-eicosapentaénoic	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

Solar drying of vegetal products and fish allowed their preservation and would facilitate their regular consumption all year long. Dried products showed interesting nutritional attributes (potassium vitamin C, protein, fat). Moreover, valorisation of fish from Bouherthma dam would contribute to improving diet, particularly by providing high level of animal proteins and fats. In fact, in Jendouba around 53,3% of calories originate from cereals. The use of sustainable methods of transformation developed in FOODLAND project combined food preservation and nutritional quality preservation.

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2.4. MAK

2.4.1. Composite flours with new local varieties: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, biofortified beans (prototype n. 12)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

A total of four products were produced. Two of these were instant (extruded) and two non-instant (raw). For each of the two categories, one of the formulations consisted 3 ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, biofortified beans and grain amaranth) and one constituted 4 ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, biofortified beans and grain amaranth).

The new food raw materials used in this project included the following:

-Grain amaranth: *Amaranthus hypodriacus* L., cream type, obtained from Mukono, Uganda in 2022-2024.

-Orange fleshed sweet potatoes: Naspot 12 obtained from in Kamuli, Uganda in 2022-2024

-Biofortified beans: NAROBAN 2, obtained from the National Crop Research Institute, Wakiso, Uganda in 2022-2024.

-Maize flour was used as an additional ingredient for 2 (one instant and one non-instant) of the four composite flours developed. Maize, was used instead of pumpkins, which had been proposed as an ingredient for composite flours, because it was more available, inexpensive and the other novel ingredients (orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans) can provided similar nutrients to the ones supplied by pumpkins.

2. Results

The developed composite flours were generally higher in proteins, dietary fibre, beta-carotenes, iron, zinc and phytochemicals compared to a commercial flour, widely consumed in Uganda (Tables 2.4.1.1, 2.4.1.2 and 2.4.1.4). Extruded composite flours generally exhibited lower peak viscosities (Table 2.4.1.3) and lower phytochemicals and antioxidant capacity (Table 2.4.1.4) than the raw flours with the same ingredients. Formulations with maize were generally lower in proteins, fibre, iron, zinc and phytochemicals compared to those made from orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans only (Table 2.4.1.1, 4.2.1.2 and 4.2.1.3).

Table 2.4.1.1 Proximate composition (%) of commercial (control), raw and extruded OFSP-based composite flours

Sample	Moisture	Crude protein	Dietary fibre	Ash	Crude fat	Carbohydrates
COMM	*	15.45 ^c ±0.02	0.46 ^e ±0.08	*	*	*
RF1	*	18.16 ^a ±0.81	4.04 ^a ±0.05	*	*	*

RF2	*	17.55 ^{ab} ± 0.50	3.39 ^b ± 0.16	*	*	*
EF1	*	16.39 ^{bc} ± 0.03	2.15 ^c ± 0.08	*	*	*
EF2	*	16.13 ^c ± 0.43	1.45 ^d ± 0.19	*	*	*

Results are presented as means ± standard deviation. Means in the same columns with different superscripts are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different. COMM: commercial composite flour, RF1 and RF2 are raw composite formulations, EF1 and EF2 are extruded composite formulations

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.1.2 Content of selected micronutrients for flours containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans

Sample	Beta carotene (mg/ 100g)	Iron (mg/100 g)	Zinc (mg/100 g)
RF1	1.27 ^a ± 0.5	*	*
RF2	1.36 ^a ± 0.4	*	*
EF1	0.88 ^b ± 0.4	*	*
EF2	1.01 ^b ± 0.4	*	*

Results are presented as means ± standard deviation. Means in the same columns with different superscripts are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different. RF1 and RF2 are raw composite formulations, EF1 and EF2 are extruded composite formulations

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.1.3. Pasting properties of control and OFSP-based composite flours

Sample ID	Peak viscosity (RVU)	Trough (RVU)	Breakdown (RVU)	Final viscosity (RVU)	Setback (RVU)	Peak time (min)	Pasting temp (°C)
COMM	2449 ^a ± 7.94	*	*	*	*	*	*
RF1	362.00 ^c ± 4.00	*	*	*	*	*	*
RF2	432.33 ^b ± 8.14	*	*	*	*	*	*
EF1	125.33 ^e ± 7.77	*	*	*	*	*	*
EF2	216.33 ^d ± 4.51	*	*	*	*	*	*

Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation. Means in the same columns with different superscripts are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different. COMM: commercial composite flour (control), RF1 and RF2: raw composite formulations, EF1 and EF2: extruded composite formulations, ND: not detected

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.1.4. Phytochemicals content of control and OFSP-based composite flours

Sample ID	Total antioxidants (mg AAE/100 g)	Flavonoids (mg CatE/100 g)	Total phenolics (mg GAE/100 g)	Tannins (mg CatE/100 g)	Phytates (mg/100 g)
COMM	137.45 ^d ±9.58	225.47 ^b ±6.98	*	*	*
RF1	376.63 ^a ±3.52	575.38 ^a ±5.15	*	*	*
RF2	327.70 ^{ab} ±5.27	339.42 ^{ab} ±4.99	*	*	*
EF1	313.67 ^b ±7.51	58.17 ^c ±3.19	*	*	*
EF2	173.536 ^c ±1.40	30.82 ^d ±3.19	*	*	*

Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation. Means in the same columns with different superscripts are significantly ($p < 0.05$) different. COMM: commercial composite flour (control), RF1 and RF2 are raw composite formulations and EF1 and EF2 are extruded composite formulations.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Extruded samples generally exhibited higher water absorption capacity, higher solubility and lower swelling power than the raw samples (Table 2.4.1.5). The differences in nutrient content of the different flours are attributable to differences in composition of the raw ingredients used. Of the components used, maize flour (refined) is generally lower in nutrients and phytochemicals, phytochemicals than other ingredients used in product formulation (Chikpah et al., 2020; Kamotho, 2020; Neela & Fanta, 2019). The differences between extruded and raw flour can be attributed to starch pregelatinisation that occurs during extrusion (Akinwale et al., 2017). The lower phytochemicals content of extruded samples on the other hand is attributable to degradation of these components during the high temperatures recorded during extrusion (Patil & Kaur, 2018). Extruded flours also contained lower protein content. This is attributable to protein denaturation and apparent partial loss of certain amino acids and nitrogenous compounds on heating that occurs during extrusion cooking (Mosibo et al., 2022; Omosebi et al., 2018). Extruded formulations had lower values of beta carotene compared to those of raw formulations. This could be attributed to thermal degradation of beta carotene due to high temperature of extrusion (Akande et al. 2017; Waramboi et al., 2013).

Table 2.4.1.5. Functional properties of OFSP-based composite flours

Sample ID	Bulk density (g/mL)	WAC (%)	OAC (%)	WAI (g/g)	WSI (%)	Swelling power (%)
COMM	0.776 ^a ±0.009	*	*	*	*	*
RF1	0.592 ^b ±0.005	*	*	*	*	*
RF2	0.606 ^b ±0.005	*	*	*	*	*
EF1	0.527 ^c ±0.008	*	*	*	*	*

EF2	0.515 ^c ±0.002	*	*	*	*	*
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Results are presented as mean ± S.D of samples. Means in the same column with the same superscript were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) different. COMM: commercial composite flour, RF1 and RF2 are raw composite flours, EF1 and EF2 are extruded composite flours. WAC: water absorption capacity, OAC: oil absorption capacity, WAI: water absorption index and WSI: water solubility index

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Sensory evaluation results (Table 2.4.1.6) show that the developed flours were all generally acceptable, with score for all attributes being >5 (on a 9-point hedonic scale) for porridge obtained with each flour.

Table 2.4.1.6. Sensory acceptability of porridges from OFSP-based composite flours and a commercial flour

Sample ID	Colour	Aroma	Mouthfeel	Taste	Aftertaste	Overall acceptability
COMM	*	*	*	*	*	7.14 ^a ±1.16
RF1	*	*	*	*	*	5.62 ^b ±1.67
RF2	*	*	*	*	*	6.81 ^a ±1.20
EF1	*	*	*	*	*	5.14 ^b ±1.92
EF2	*	*	*	*	*	6.87 ^a ±1.08
p-value	*	*	*	*	*	<0.0001

Values are mean ± standard deviation (n=50). Means in the same columns with different superscripts are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). RF1: Raw composite formulation without maize, RF2: Raw composite formulation containing maize, EF1: Extruded composite formulation without maize and EF2: Extruded composite formulation containing maize

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

The most consumed flour in Uganda is refined maize flour, which is low in fibre, vitamins, minerals and bioactive phytochemicals. Refined maize flour is mostly composed of starch and hence supplies empty calories. It's contribution to the nutritional needs of different groups is therefore limited. This is partly responsible for the high incidence of under-nutrition and micro-nutrient deficiencies recorded in the country, as reported in D2.5. The developed nutrient enhanced flours have a higher potential compared to refined maize only flour, to address high under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiencies and over-nutrition, the co-existing nutrition problems that Uganda faces. The relatively high content of phytochemicals and fibre in the developed flours make them particularly suitable for consumption by adults and the elderly, who are at risk of developing obesity and associated non-communicable diseases. The flours, therefore, contribute to addressing the nutritional recommendations developed for Uganda under the FoodLAND project

(D2.6). The markedly low dietary bulk (low gruel density) recorded for extruded flours make them suitable for children since these require foods that are dense in energy and nutrients.

However, it is important to underline the need for mycotoxin analysis in cereals as critical aspect to ensure food safety and the presence of antinutritional factors deriving from legumes.

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2.4.2. Snacks from new local varieties/species: orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth, biofortified beans (prototype n. 20)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Baked doughnuts (commonly referred to as *daddies* in Uganda) were made using 40% non instant orange fleshed, grain amaranth and biofortied beans flour (made as described in section 2.4.1) and 60% wheat. Other ingredient used were wheat flour, sugar, eggs and butter.

2. Results

Table 2.4.2.1. reports the nutritional composition of baked snacks with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed based composite flour. The produced snacks contained relatively high levels of protein and fibre compared to snacks made from only refined wheat (Godswill, 2019). This can be attributed to the relatively high nutritional value of the composite flour used to replace wheat. The snack is generally high in fat, which makes it a high energy product, that's suitable for very active individuals such as school-age children. These snacks (*daddies*) are commonly consumed by children in boarding schools. These are unlikely to have a problem with excessive energy intake. The high energy content of the snack is therefore not likely to lead to overweight and obesity.

The snacks' sensory scores for all attributes (Table 2.4.2.2) were relatively high (≥ 7.8 on a 9point scale). This shows that the product was well accepted by panelists. This is indicative of high potential for market acceptability.

Table 2.4.2.1. Nutritional composition of baked snacks with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed based composite flour

Water %	Protein %	Ash %	Fibre %	Fat %	Carbohydrates %	β carotene mg/100g	Iron mg/100g	Zinc mg/100g
3.81±0.11	18.72±0.38	*	*	20.23±0.16	*	*	*	*

n=3

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.2.2 Sensory evaluation of baked snacks with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed based composite flour

Appearance	Taste	Overall acceptability
*	*	8.4±1.1

n= 35

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

The developed snack scored highly in sensory evaluation. This shows that the product has high potential for success at commercial level. Nutritionally, the product has a high content of proteins and fat and is nutritionally superior to the snacks commonly consumed in Uganda. They therefore have potential to contribute to a reduction in the high level of under-nutrition reported in D 25. They are particularly suitable for addressing the problem of protein energy malnutrition, which is prevalent in Uganda, especially among children. The snack could therefore be promoted for consumption among children and is a suitable snack for children attending boarding schools, since they store well, are not voluminous, are convenient and are energy dense. However, it is important to underline the need to determine mycotoxin content in cereals as critical aspect to ensure food safety, antinutritional compounds in legumes and a full amino acid profile for a proper nutritional characterization.

These snacks do not necessarily target adults and the elderly, the main focus for nutrition guidelines developed for Uganda (D26).

4. References

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2.4.3. Noodles from new local varieties/species: Orange-fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans partially substituting wheat (prototype n. 25d)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Biofortified beans and orange-fleshed sweet potatoes were used to substitute 27% of wheat in a formulation for making noodles. Details of the orange fleshed sweet potatoes and grain amaranth used are provided below:

-Orange fleshed sweet potatoes: NASOPOT 8, obtained from farmers in Kamuli district, Uganda in 2022-2024.

-Biofortified beans: NARABEAN 3: Obtained from the National Crop Science Research Institute, Wakiso district, Uganda in 2022-2024.

-Other ingredients included wheat, baking powder, salt and water.

2. Results

Noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans were found to contain higher levels of dietary fibre, proteins and β -carotene (Table 2.4.3.1 and Table 2.4.3.2), compared

to noodles made using conventional formulation (no wheat substitution). This is attributable to the higher content of these nutrients in orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans than in wheat (Adoko et al., 2021; Neela and Fanta, 2019; Mahmoud et al., 2012). The cooking properties (Table 2.4.3.3) of the noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans also slightly differed from that of with wheat as the sole flour. The differences in cooking properties are attributable to differences in composition of the ingredients, mainly due to differences in starch content (Deng et al., 2023).

Table 2.4.3.1 Proximate analysis for the orange fleshed sweet potato and biofortified beans containing noodles

Sample	% Composition						
	Moisture	Ash	Dietary fibre	Fat	Protein	Carbohydrates*	β-carotene (mg/100g)
Control	*	*	0.52 ^a ± 0.010	*	*	*	0.04 ^a ± 0.23 ¹
Nutrient enhanced noodles	*	*	11.77 ^b ± 0.67	*	*	*	0.54 ^b ± 0.01 ¹

Values are means ± standard deviation of at least three determinations (n=3). Means in a column with different superscript are statistically different (p ≤ 0.05). *Derived by difference.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.3.2. β-carotene, iron and zinc of noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans

Component (mg/100g)	Content
β-carotene	0.54 ± 0.01
Iron	*
Zinc	*

Table 2.4.3.3. Cooking properties and colour of wheat noodles (control) and composite noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans

Property	Developed composite noodles	Control
Cooking time (s)	1083.80 ^b ± 8.82	915.20 ^a ± 4.45
Cooking loss (%)	*	*
Cooking yield (%)	*	*
Colour	*	*
L*	*	*
a*	*	*
b*	*	*

Values are means \pm standard deviation of at least three determinations ($n=3$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.4.3.4 Sensory properties of wheat noodles (control) and composite noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans

Property	Developed composite noodles	Control
Appearance	*	*
Colour	*	*
Aroma	*	*
Taste	*	*
Mouthfeel	*	*
Aftertaste	*	*
Overall acceptability	7.8 ^a \pm 1.06	8.0 ^a \pm 0.95

Values are means \pm standard deviation of at least three determinations ($n=50$). Scores for each sensory attribute based on a 9-point hedonic scale: 1=disliked extremely, 2=disliked very much, 3=disliked moderately, 4=disliked slightly, 5=neither liked nor disliked, 6=liked slightly, 7=liked moderately, 8=liked very much, 9=liked extremely

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Based on sensory evaluation scores, the developed noodles were highly acceptable (Table 2.4.3.4). This shows that the product is likely to be accepted by the market, if produced at commercial scale.

3. Conclusions

On the basis of the observation that Uganda faces co-existence of under nutrition, nutritional deficiency and over nutrition (as reported in D25), food products high in micro and macro nutrients as well as foods high in phytochemicals are needed, to specially target persons at risk of under nutrition. The developed noodles are aligned with this need since they are high in protein, fibre and micro nutrients. These therefore have the potential to contribute to alleviation of micro nutrient deficiency and non-communicable diseases associated with over nutrition. However, it is important to underline the need to determine mycotoxin content in cereals as critical aspect to ensure food safety, antinutritional compounds in legumes and a full amino acid profile for a proer nutritional characterization.

The noodles therefore can contribute to addressing the nutritional recommendations developed for Uganda under the FoodLAND project (D2.6). Sensory evaluation scores for the noodles were relatively high. This reveals high potential for market acceptance of the product. If commercialized and widely consumed, this product would contribute to addressing the key nutrition problems

Uganda faces and create demand for the crops, hence contributing to creating market for farm produce.

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2.5. UoM

2.5.1. Composite flours with new local varieties: moringa and teff grain (prototype n. 13)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The history of teff and its role in the earliest agricultural societies in the Horn of Africa are poorly understood. It is believed that teff was domesticated in ancient Axum in the northern Ethiopian highlands, where its centers of origin and diversity are located (Seyfu, 1997, Seyfu, 1993, Costanza et al. 1980; Demissie 2001; Vavilov 1951). Archaeological teff remains from Ona Nagast village (D'Andrea, 2008) nearby Axum are examined in detail. Early cultivators were likely selecting for increased branching and higher percentage seed set under conditions of minimal tillage.

Teff is a hardy low-risk field crop that grows well withstanding insect pests and diseases (Seyfu, 1993). Farmers' preferences to grow tef and sustained demand from urban consumers have increased the production to an average of two million hectares a year, setting it in the forefront in terms of cultivated area (Hailu et al., 2001).

Compared with other food crops, it is important national diet of Ethiopia highly-valued by farmers and consumers (Hailu et al., 2001). The best quality Enjera, a staple diet of most Ethiopians, is made out of teff flour. It is always eaten in the whole grain form. The germ and bran are consumed along with the endosperm (Demeke and Di-Marcantonio, 2013).

Moringa is a fast-growing and drought-resistant multipurpose tree of high economic and commercial importance with diverse benefits both for humans, livestock and the environment especially water purification (Paliwal and Sharma 2011; Dhakad et al. 2019; Elghandour et al. 2023). It also involves promising applications in food products (Saucedo-Pompa et al. 2018). The edible parts of the plant include leaves, stalks and stem but the leaves are the most used part (Leone et al. 2015).

The inputs, management process and output/product storage for teff still remain to be less researched. There are limited new varieties, and insufficient availability of early generation seed for teff production. Inappropriate seeding rates, planting techniques, poor fertilizer application, poor crop-protection techniques, and poor awareness of mechanized technologies are among the limitation in the agronomic management process.

Furthermore, lack of organized user groups (cooperatives), storage facilities, skills on storage and small-scale processing, and poor market linkages are associated limitations in the teff grain food products. These limitations call for concerted efforts of doing coordinated technological research to solve the problems in the process of teff production and product marketing. Likewise, synthesis of novel food products through compositing of teff flour with other nutritionally important ingredients such as Moringa leaf powder will enhance its acceptance in the global markets.

In this composite flours research, we have started with cleaning, sieving, and milling in obtaining teff flour and Moringa powder for consumption. Blending teff-Moringa flour results in five treatments (i.e., teff100%, teff90:10Moringa, teff80:20Moringa, teff70:30Moringa, teff60:40Moringa, teff50:50Moringa, and Moringa100%). The independent teff and moringa leaf samples were grinded to pass through 1mm diameter sieve and analyzed (preliminary) in the laboratory at UoM.

Milling teff and moringa powder was continued using 0.85mm and 0.50mm diameters sieves, as shown in Fig 2.5.1.1. The grains were milled using two types of sieves to give coarse and fine milled teff flour meant to serve as ingredients for various value-added products.

The teff flower and moringa leaf powder were then blended for further prepared for the physical and nutritional laboratory analysis of the composite or blended flours.

Figure 2.5.1.1. Teff flour (milling in 0.85 mm sieve diameter and 0.50 mm sieve diameter)

2. Results

The nutritional components of teff flour and moringa leaf powder are reported in Table 2.5.1.1. Teff flour showed high carbohydrate and protein contents, while Moringa leaf powder showed high ash, fiber, and protein contents.

Table 2.5.1.1. Nutritional composition of Teff flour and Moringa leaf powder (Laelay Machew/Axum-Ethiopia)

	Ash g/100g	Fiber g/100g	Fat g/100g	Protein g/100g	Carbohydrate g/100g
Teff	*	*	*	12.85±2.01	*
Moringa	*	*	*	17.63±3.62	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.5.1.2 reports the content of minerals in the teff and moringa. Moringa flour showed a very high calcium content, significantly higher compared to Teff ones. Iron was higher in Teff compared to Moringa, while other minerals comparable among the 2 types of flours.

Table 2.5.2.2. Mineral contents of Teff flour and Moringa leaf powder (Laelay Machew/Axum-Ethiopia)

Zn mg/kg	Fe mg/kg	Cu mg/kg	Mn mg/kg	Ca mg/kg	Mg mg/kg

Teff	*	182.50±8.91	*	*	253.33±10.37	*
Moringa	*	38.93±1.74	*	*	3284.30±29.98	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

According to the rural and urban consumers' survey results, both the women and household dietary diversity score was far below the minimum recommendation. The most consumed food groups were cereals which are more of energy rich while their micronutrient content is minimal. Furthermore, animal source consumption both among under-five children and adults were low. Low intake of such foods was reported as one of the major risk factors to micronutrient nutrient deficiency including zinc, calcium and magnesium. Low intakes of such micronutrients among under-five children were strongly associated with chronic malnutrition and stunting in which more than 48% of them are short for their age.

Moreover, low intake of foods rich in protein, including animal source food, among children under five, women of reproductive age group, and adolescent girls lead to high burden of acute malnutrition and wasting. The high protein of both moringa and teff will also help in improving the protein intake among the target community.

The preparation of teff and moringa composite flours allows to complement their nutritional quality and obtain a product that is suitable for feeding nutritionally vulnerable population groups including infants, children, the sick, the elderly and those that are health conscious. The flours would thus contribute to alleviating the nutritional problems of under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency and obesity, which are public health problems (as reported in D2.5).

However, before positioning in the market, it is important to underline the need to determine mycotoxin content in the cereal as critical aspect to ensure food safety.

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2.6. UoN

2.6.1. Composite flours with new local varieties: therapeutic powder for diabetic people (prototype n. 14)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Locally available mature ripe tree tomato fruits of the red and yellow cultivars were procured from five different traders at Marigiti market, Nairobi County in Kenya. The fruits were pooled into either red or yellow batches and transported to the Department of Food Science, Nutrition and Technology at the University of Nairobi and characterized before drying into a powder product, using both solar tunnel and an innovative greenhouse dryer. Drying of Tree tomato fruits was carried out at the University of Nairobi and at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited

(KEPC) premises in Kitui Town, Kitui Food Hub using the Innovative solar drier. Over 40 people who included local farmers and processors were able to learn about the new technology during the validation process. Tree tomato fruits were pulped then dried using the drier, milled into powder then packaged. Feedback on the innovative solar drier and the drying process was collected from the respondents on the conducted activities, outputs reached, outcomes and impact of the innovative technology.

2. Results

Raw material characterization

Table 2.6.1.1: Yield (%) of the tree tomato fruits and Yield Ratio and relative statistical data

Variety	Pulp yield	By-products		Yield Ratio (Pulp/By-products)
		Peels yield	Seeds yield	
Red fresh	82.34±0.97 ^a	*	*	4.00±0.43 ^a
Yellow fresh	83.20±1.47 ^a	*	*	3.18±0.00 ^b
Overall Mean	*	*	*	*
Range	*	*	*	*
standard deviation	*	*	*	*
Coefficient of variation (%)	*	*	*	*
P-Value	*	*	*	*

Values (means± standard errors) with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The pulp to seeds ratio was higher ($p < 0.05$) in the red variety (4.00) than in the yellow variety (3.17) and both fruit varieties had significant number of seeds inside the pericarp, as shown in the cross-sectional image (Figure 2.6.1.1 and 2.6.1.2)

Figure 2.6.1.1: Cross sectional view of Red Tree Tomato

Figure 2.6.1.2: Cross sectional view of Yellow Tree Tomato

Before peeling, significant ($p < 0.05$) color differences were found across the L^* , b^* , Chroma^* , Hue angle^* color parameters, with the yellow variety having higher values compared to the red variety (Table 2.6.1.2)

Table 2.6.1.2: Color of tree tomato skin before peeling

Variety	Skin Color (Before Peeling)				
	L^*	a^*	b^*	Chroma^*	Hue angle^*
Red Fresh	*	*	*	*	*
Yellow Fresh	*	*	*	*	*
$\Delta\text{Chromacity}$ coordinate	*	*	*	*	*
$\Delta\text{Chromacity}$ coordinate ²	*	*	*	*	*
ΔE (Total color Difference)	*				

Color values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Values with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

** Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]*

After peeling the fruits, the surface color of the flesh was yellow and there was significant difference in the L^* coordinate, with higher lightness (L^*) value in the red variety as compared to the yellow variety ($p < 0.005$) (Table 2.6.1.3).

Table 2.6.1.3: Color of tree tomato surface after peeling

Variety	Surface (After Peeling)				
	L^*	a^*	b^*	Chroma^*	Hue angle^*
Coordinates					

Red Fresh	*	*	*	*	*
Yellow Fresh	*	*	*	*	*
ΔChromacity coordinate	*	*	*	*	*
ΔChromacity coordinate²	*	*	*	*	*
ΔE (Total color Difference)	*				

Color values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Values with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Important differences were observed between the proximate compositions of the red and the yellow tree tomato varieties (Table 2.6.1.4). The red variety showed a significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher content of crude fat and total ash compared to the yellow variety. Moreover, the yellow variety showed a higher ($p < 0.0001$) crude protein content compared to the red variety.

Table 2.6.1.4: Proximate composition of red and yellow tree tomato varieties

Variety/ Attribute	Moisture Content (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Fibre (%)	Ash (%)	Carbohy- drate (%)	Energy (Kcal/100 g)
Red fresh	*	0.98±0.02 ^b	0.09±0.00 ^a	*	*	*	*
Yellow fresh	*	1.70±0.01 ^a	0.02±0.00 ^b	*	*	*	*
O. Mean	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Range	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Std. Dev.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
C.V (%)	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
P-Value	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Values (means ± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$). The values were determined on a wet weight basis.

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

No significant differences were observed between the pH values, total soluble solids (TSS), moisture and energy content of both varieties. The acidity level (citric acid) was significantly different ($p = 0.0001$), with the red variety having higher level compared to the yellow variety. The sugar acidity ratio was significantly different ($p = 0.018$), with a lower mean value for the red variety (Table 2.6.1.5).

Table 2.6.1.5: Chemical attributes

Attribute/ Variety	pH	Sugars (%)	TSS (%)	Acidity (%)	Sugar/Acidity Ratio
Red fresh	3.90±0.02 ^a	*	*	*	*
Yellow fresh	3.84±0.01 ^a	*	*	*	*
Overall Mean	*	*	*	*	*
Range	*	*	*	*	*
standard deviation	*	*	*	*	*
C. V (%)	*	*	*	*	*
P-Value	*	*	*	*	*

Values (means± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The minerals content (Table 2.6.1.6) of the yellow and red fresh varieties showed statistical differences ($P < 0.05$) for all compounds except that for phosphorus.

Table 2.6.1.6: Mineral content (mg/kg F.W)

Variety/ Attribute	Phosphorus	Potassium	Iron	Manganese	Magnesium	Copper	Zinc
Yellow fresh	*	*	36.53±0.51 ^b	*	*	*	*
Red fresh	*	*	59.53±1.59 ^a	*	*	*	*
Overall Mean	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Range	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
Std Dev.	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
C.V (%)	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
P-Value	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Values (means± standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The functional properties differed depending on the variety (Table 2.6.1.8). The phenols and flavonoids mean values were not statistically different ($p > 0.05$). The yellow variety was richer in vitamin A (retinol) compared to the red variety but had a lower content of vitamin C. Antioxidant activity was significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher in the red variety compared to the yellow variety (Table 2.6.1.7).

Table 2.6.1.7: Bioactive compounds content

Variety/Attribute	Phenols (mg Gallic Acid equivalent/g)	Flavonoids (mg catechin (CAT) equivalent/g)	Antioxidant activity (μmol TEAC/100 g FW)	Vitamin C (mg/100g)	Vitamin A (mcg RAE/100g)
Yellow fresh	*	*	*	31.74 \pm 0.45 ^b	4.70 \pm 0.09 ^a
Red fresh	*	*	*	34.89 \pm 0.30 ^a	2.75 \pm 0.05 ^b
Overall Mean	*	*	*	*	*
Range	*	*	*	*	*
Standard deviation	*	*	*	*	*
CV. (%)	*	*	*	*	*
P-Value	*	*	*	*	*

Values (means \pm standard errors) with different superscripts in a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Powder product characterization

There was no evident major trend in L^* , a^* , b^* , c^* and ΔE^* values of tree tomato powder from both dryers but the chromacity values were higher in the innovative greenhouse (IG) dryer as compared to the solar tunnel (ST) dryer (Figure 2.6.1.3). The drying system only significantly affected the h^* and of the fruit powder which was higher for the ST (30.33) compared to the IG (25.63) dryer.

Figure 2.6.1.3 Colour parameter of tomato powder obtained with innovative greenhouse (IG) and solar tunnel (ST)

Values with different superscripts are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$)

The physical quality parameters varied as shown in table 2.6.1.8. There was no significant difference $p < 0.001$ of the moisture content and water activity on both dryers. The average pH value was significantly ($p < 0.001$) different with higher values recorded on the solar tunnel (3.88) as compared to the innovative greenhouse dryer (3.86).

Table 2.6.1.8: Effect of Solar tunnel (ST) and Innovative greenhouse (IG) dryers on Physical properties of tree tomato powder

Physical Quality Parameters	Dryer		p-value
	Innovative greenhouse (IG)	Solar tunnel (ST)	
Moisture Content	8.66±0.929 ^a	8.85±0.929 ^a	$p > 0.05$
Water activity (aw)	*	*	*
pH	*	*	*

Values (means± standard errors) with different superscripts across the row are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.6.1.9 shows the technological quality parameters of the tree tomato powder from both dryers. It can be deduced that the type of dryer did not have a significant effect on the rehydration ratio and water activity of the powder product. Significant difference ($p < 0.001$) was recorded for the water solubility (%) at 50°C, with higher value of for the solar tunnel dryer (98.53%) compared to the innovative greenhouse one (97.68%).

Table 2.6.1.9: Effect of Solar tunnel (ST) and Innovative greenhouse (IG) dryers on Technological properties of tree tomato powder

Technological Quality Parameters	Dryer		p-value
	Innovative greenhouse (IG)	Solar tunnel (ST)	
Rehydration Ratio	4.42±0.000 ^a	4.47±0.000 ^a	$p > 0.05$
Hygroscopicity	*	*	*
Water Solubility % (WS %)	25°C	*	$p > 0.05$
	50 °C	*	$p < 0.001$
	80 °C	*	$p > 0.05$

Values (means± standard errors) with different superscripts across the row are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P < 0.05$).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed in the functional properties analyzed for both dryers (Table 2.6.1.10) except for the total polyphenols. Flavonoids were higher (4.18 mg/100g) in the solar tunnel dryer as compared with the innovative greenhouse dryer which recorded a

value of 3.96. The average Antioxidant activity for the innovative greenhouse dryer was 1672.37 mg/100g while that from solar tunnel was 1661.10 mg/100g. The vitamins content was significantly ($p < 0.001$) different for both dryers, with higher values of Vitamin A and C recorded in the innovative greenhouse dryer (48.77 mg/100g and 348.89 mg/100g respectively) as compared to the solar tunnel dryer (45.48 mg/100g and 338.02 mg/100g respectively).

Table 2.6.1.10: Effect of Solar tunnel (ST) and Innovative greenhouse (IG) dryers on Functional properties of tree tomato powder

Functional attributes	Dryer		p-value
	Innovative greenhouse (IG)	Solar tunnel (ST)	
Total Phenols (mg/100g)	*	*	*
Flavonoids (mg/100g)	*	*	*
Antioxidant activity (mg/100g)	*	*	*
Vitamin A (mg/100g)	48.77±0.000 ^a	45.48±0.000 ^b	$p < 0.001$
Vitamin C (mg/100g)	348.89±0.000 ^a	338.02±0.000 ^b	$p < 0.001$

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

The average sensory test scores for the tree tomato powder from both dryers are presented in Figure 2.6.1.4 for each attribute tested. The standard deviation values of the panelists ranged from 0.428 to 0.635 implying they were in agreement on the attributes. The sensory analysis results showed the innovative greenhouse (IG) dryer product was more superior in terms of appearance, aroma, taste and general acceptability with an average hedonic scale rating of 4.3,4.59,4.81,4.78,4.95 as compared to the solar tunnel drier which recorded 3.83,4.4,4.43,4.54,4.4 respectively.

Figure 2.6.1.4: Effect of Solar tunnel (ST) and Innovative greenhouse (IG) dryers on Sensory quality of tree tomato powder

3. Conclusions

A shelf stable product with excellent physical, technological, functional and sensory attributes was achieved through different solar drying methods. From the presented findings, the powder is nutrient dense and can therefore be used as a therapeutic powder for diabetic people as suggested in D2.5. Consider development of novel therapeutic products as supportive strategic products in the management of NCDs, such as diabetes. As per the Nutritional recommendations (D2.6) for technological innovators, manufacturers and social media, the exploitable results developed from solar drying need uptake and subsequent sustainability to provide a platform for exploitation of these novel technologies generated. In the process of exploiting results, manufacturers should play an important role through tree tomato fruits value addition the nutrient dense shelf stable product and making available, for uptake in the markets.

4. References

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2.6.2. Snacks from new local varieties/species: cereal-based snacks for children (prototype n. 23)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd) is an exotic pseudocereal in Kenya; it was introduced in the 1950s, but the adoption of the grain has largely been dismal. The quinoa seed is a nutrient-dense crop and contains protein of high biological value that is said to compete with protein found in soy bean and milk. In addition to its protein quality, quinoa is rich in essential fatty acids, vitamins and minerals as well as fiber and phytochemicals. Consumption of quinoa is increasing in countries that do not habitually grow it, though it has been introduced in Europe, North America and Africa. Where the crop is traditionally grown, in Peru and Bolivia, a consumption of 1.1.5 kg/person and 2.37 kg/person, respectively.

The plant does not belong to the Gramineae family, but the seeds can be milled into flour that can be used for processing of various products such as bread, cookies, biscuits, noodles, pasta, pancakes and others. Health-conscious consumers prefer quinoa over wheat products, due to its gluten free nature.

One of the researchers demonstrated that consumption of 40g of Quinoa meets a significant proportion of the recommended daily allowances (RDA) for vitamins, minerals, and essential

amino acids. Based on this scientific evidence, a quinoa product (mandazi) that intended to supply at least 40 grams of quinoa to children attending early child development education in Kenya was developed. Kitui county still faces food insecurity challenges, while a slightly higher stunting than the national prevalence of is noted for the County.

To obtain the mandazi, wheat flour was blended with quinoa to make the composite flour in a ratio of quinoa to wheat flour of 70:30. Dry ingredients were mixed first i.e., flour, sugar, salt, and baking powder, and yeast. Then ghee was mixed with the dry ingredients to obtain a sandy appearance. Then water was added until a desirable dough was achieved. The dough was let to rest for approximately 30 minutes, after which it was reworked to remove air pockets created by yeast fermentation. The dough was then divided into 240 grams balls which were flattened to obtain a thickness of 5mm. The flattened dough was cut to four halves each, approximately weighing 60 grams. The mandazi were then deep fried in heated oil (liquid palm oil) until the colour achieved was light brown (Figure 2.6.2.1). The mandazi were then kept in a bucket to cool. During the manufacture of the mandazi, no preservatives were used.

Figure 2.6.2.1: Quinoa snack (mandazi)

The study was designed to enhance the nutritional diversity of under-five children and increase intakes of high biological value protein among the children in the region. Sensory evaluation of the product was carried out. The purpose of the study was to evaluate the shelf-life of quinoa-wheat composite flour (quinoa at 70%), and to assess the shelf-life of mandazi prepared from substituted flour.

2. Results

Proximate composition of quinoa flour and mandazi is shown in Table 2.6.2.1. The moisture content of quinoa flour used for mandazi preparation was $5.32 \pm 0.19\%$ while that of the mandazi was $15.1 \pm 0.69\%$. Fat content of the composite flour was $1.28 \pm 0.05\%$ while that of the mandazi was $18.28 \pm 0.04\%$. The energy of composite flour was 371.64 ± 1.13 Kcal/100g while that of the

mandazi was 414.4+2.29 Kcal/100g. The protein content was 13.11+0.59% and 5.63+0.32% for flour and Mandazi, respectively.

Table 2.6.2.1: Proximate composition of quinoa (composite flour 70%) and 30% Wheat flour and mandazi snacks

	Quinoa Flour		Quinoa Mandazi	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std
Moisture (%)	5.32	0.19	15.1	0.69
Fibre (%)	*	*	*	*
Ash (%)	*	*	*	*
Protein (%)	*	*	*	*
Fat (%)	*	*	*	*
Carbohydrate (%)	*	*	*	*
Energy (kcal/100g)	*	*	*	*

Expressed per 100g of sample; std Standard deviation

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

The study established that a nutrient rich snack from quinoa-wheat composite flour (quinoa at 70%), can be prepared and used to improve nutritional status of preschool children in Kenya, where poor dietary habits diet (D2.5), such as over consumption of fast foods, ultra-processed packaged salty snacks, sugar sweetened beverages (soda) and sweets occurs. As per the nutritional recommendations (D 2.6), adopting the healthy snacking behaviour by consuming the nutrient rich quinoa snack will reduce consumption of highly processed salted snacks.

However, it is important to underline the need to determine mycotoxin content in the quinoa as critical aspect to ensure food safety.

4. References

Vilcacundo, R., & Hernández-Ledesma, B. (2017). Nutritional and biological value of quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd.). *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 14, 1-6.

2.6.3 Therapeutic food (prototype n. 24)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The quinoa-based porridge flour was formulated from a mix of quinoa and maize flour at a 75-25% ratio, respectively. The quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) grain was sourced from Malawi, while the maize (*Zea mays*) was locally sourced (from Kenya). The proximate composition of the quinoa

grain was determined at the University of Nairobi Food Chemistry Labs while that of the maize was adopted from the Kenyan Food Composition Tables 2018 (FAO/Government of Kenya, 2018).

2. Results

The composition of the raw materials and final product was determined using three methods: Lab analysis, a food composition table (Kenya Food Composition Tables 2018) and Nutri survey.

The results are shown in table 2.6.3.1.

Table 2.6.3.1: Composition of the quinoa, maize and the composite flour

Ingredient/ Product	Moisture %	Protein g/100g	Fat g/100g	Carbohy- drate g/100g	Fibre g/100g	Calcium mg/100g	Iron mg/100g	Zinc mg/100g
Quinoa	*	13	*	*	*	*	*	*
Maize*	*	8	*	*	*	*	*	*
Quinoa- Maize flour**	*	12	*	*	*	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

After formulation, the quinoa enriched porridge flour nutritional properties were validated in a feeding trial conducted in Kitui County among preschool children for 5 weeks. The parameters studied were Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) and waistline. The results are as presented in the figure 2.6.3.1. There was a notable increase in MUAC and the waistline indicating that the consumption of the quinoa enriched porridge contributed to improvement in nutritional status.

Figure 2.6.3.1: Contribution of quinoa enriched porridge flour to the Nutritional Status of Children (Intervention and Control Groups; MUAC & Wasteline in cm)

3. Conclusions

The study established that the quinoa enriched porridge flour contributes to improved nutritional status of preschool children in Kenya. This will contribute to solve the most common nutritional challenges in children of low-quality undiversified diets as described in D 2.5 of low consumption of nutrient dense foods. As per the nutritional recommendation (D2.6), the enriched porridge flour which is particularly rich in high biological value protein and fibre will contribute to improve the diet quality by diversifying it, to ensure inclusion of the per day recommended seven food groups to meet the minimum target of four out of seven.

4. References

FAO/Government of Kenya. (2018). Kenya Food Composition Tables. <http://www.fao.org/3/I9120EN/i9120en.pdf>

2.7. NARO

2.7.1. Dried products: dried fish (prototype n. 15a), fish powder (prototype n. 16)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Fish and fishery products represent valuable sources of nutrients and contribute to diversified and healthy diets (FAO, 2013). Fish meat is a source of high biological value proteins, polyunsaturated

fatty acids, vitamins and minerals, with the minerals mainly concentrated in the bones (Kabahenda *et al.*, 2011). Fish is highly perishable due to high levels of moisture, less connective tissues, low levels of non-protein compounds among others. As such, at artisanal level, lack of ice and freezing facilities compel fish farmers to dehydrate the harvested fish using low cost preservation methods namely: smoking, drying, salting or a combination of the three. Drying uses convection heat transfer in the open or in solar tents or mechanical drier.

Four fish species were obtained from the fish farm in Kakiri, central Uganda. The fish species were: Nile Tilapia, Catfish, Barbus and Labeo sp. These were sedated and filleted from near head to tail. The obtained fillets were minced and then homogenised in a micro food processor to obtain a fine paste which were kept in a freezer for proximate analysis. The carcasses were oven dried at 60 °C overnight, and then taken to the laboratory for micronutrient analysis.

Nile Tilapia, African Catfish, and Barbus sp. were used to obtain processed fish. The NARO PAH-Safe Fish Smoking Kiln was used to obtain smoked fish with acceptable levels of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH). Salted and solar dried fish were processed by brining technique and solar tent drying, respectively.

For the fish powder, fish bones from the carcasses of Tilapia and Catfish were dried and milled into a fish bone powder. The powder is shelf-stable and rich in micronutrients.

Nile Tilapia and African Catfish carcasses were used as base material. Separate by-products were separated into respective components (parts), keeping in mind that the belly-flaps and all fatty material should be removed from carcasses, then washed with potable water at room temperature and heated at 80 °C for 15 minutes to inactivate enzymes and spoilage organisms. Excess fluid was drained and then oven dried at 60 °C until brittle ($\leq 10\%$ moisture content). Milling was performed using a hammer mill, made with food grade materials with a sieve mesh size of 0.5mm. Approximately 50g of sample was retained for proximate and micronutrient composition analysis using standard methods (AOAC, 2005).

2. Results

Proximate composition and physical characteristics of raw materials

Proximate composition and physical characteristics of Tilapia, Barbus and Catfish are shown in Table 2.7.1.1. Dry matter content varied between 19.2 and 20.5 % for the three fish species. The differences in dry matter were not significant. Ash content was in the range 0.8 to 1.4% with Barbus significantly higher than Nile tilapia but not Catfish. Barbus had a relatively higher fat content compared to catfish and tilapia. Crude protein (17 – 18.5%) was not different among the three fish species.

Table 2.7.1.1. Physical characteristics and proximate composition based on fresh weight

Fish species	Physical characteristics		Proximate composition (g/100g)							
	Total Length (cm)	Avg weight (g)	Dry matter%	FAO	Ash (%)	FAO	Crude fat (%)	FAO	Crude protein (%)	FAO
Nile Tilapia	*	*	*	*	*	*	0.5±0.4	0.6–5.0	18.5±1.2	15.6–26.9
Catfish	*	*	*	*	*	*	0.7±0.7	0.3–6.3	17.0±0.5	15.4–21.3
Barbus	*	*	*	*	*	*	1.3±1.0	na	18.0±0.6	na

na – not available

Values are means ± standard deviation of at least three determinations (n=3).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

On the basis of weight, Barbus sp. was significantly heavier than Catfish and Tilapia; Catfish was intermediate while Tilapia had relatively lower weight. The Catfish and Barbus were also longer than the Tilapia in terms of total length.

The quality characteristics of the smoked, solar dried and salted fish species (Barbus sp., Nile Tilapia and African Catfish) are summarised in Table 2.7.1.2.

The smoked samples had lower moisture content and water activity compared to the solar dried and salted fish with the exception of solar dried Nile Tilapia. The catfish had higher crude fat than the other species for all products except the smoked fish. The total ash was significantly higher in the salted fish compared to the solar dried and smoked products.

Table 2.7.1.2. Quality characteristics of the smoked, solar dried and salted fish species

Product/Fish species	Quality Characteristics/Composition				
	Moisture content (%)	Water activity	Crude fat (%)	Total Ash (%)	Overall acceptability
Smoked					
Barbus sp.	*	*	12.7±2.9	*	*
Nile Tilapia	*	*	14.7±3.2	*	*
African Catfish	*	*	8.7±3.9	*	*
Solar dried					
African Catfish	*	*	16.8±2.9	*	*
Nile Tilapia	*	*	9.8±5.0	*	*
Salted					
Barbus sp.	*	*	9.5±3.6	*	*

Nile Tilapia	*	*	6.0±1.5	*	*
African Catfish	*	*	23.0±8.2	*	*

Values are means ± standard deviation of three determinations (n=3).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Shelf-life characterisation of smoked, solar-dried and salted products

TVC (Figure 2.1.1.1) of smoked Tilapia was within the Uganda National Bureau Standards acceptable specification limit of 5 log cfu/g over the 8-week storage period. However, smoked catfish was borderline within the first 4 weeks before exceeded the limit in week 6. Smoked Barbus was already borderline for TVC by the start of the shelf-life study and had already exceeded the specification limit by the second week.

Solar dried Tilapia and catfish had marginally acceptable TVC only within the first 2 weeks of storage. By the fourth week, they both had exceeded the acceptable specification limit.

Salted Tilapia was acceptable for 6 weeks of storage and only exceeded the acceptability threshold in the eighth week. Salted Barbus was marginally acceptable by the fourth week of storage while salted catfish lasted only two weeks.

Figure 2.1.1.1. Changes in Total Viable Count (TVC) of smoked, salted and solar dried products of Barbus, Tilapia and Catfish

Sensory evaluation

Figure 2.7.1.3. Mean scores for appearance, taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptability of salted fish

Figure 2.7.1.2. Changes in Yeast and Mould Count (YMC) of smoked and solar dried products of Barbus, Tilapia and Catfish

Figure 2.7.1.2 shows the changes observed in Yeast and Mould Count (YMC) of smoked and solar dried products of Barbus, Tilapia and Catfish. The YMC for smoked Tilapia was within acceptable range up to the fourth week. However, smoked catfish marginally exceeded the acceptable limit in the second week. There was a sharp increase in the YMC of smoked Barbus resulting in extremely high counts by the second week which was more than two times above the acceptable limit

Both fish species met the YMC specification limit for solar dried fish throughout the 8 week storage period although the dried Tilapia was borderline at week 6.

Sensory evaluation of smoked, solar-dried and salted products

Figure 2.7.1.3. Mean scores for appearance, taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptability of salted fish

Figure 2.7.1.3. reports the results of sensorial evaluation of salted fish. Generally, Tilapia had higher mean scores in all the sensory attributes as compared to catfish. The scores for both Tilapia and Catfish were above the mean values from week 0 up to week 4. However, in the sixth week, African Catfish had already developed bad odor and become slimy in texture. Therefore, it was not included in further sensory analysis. The quality and safety of salted fish needs attention given that the production and distribution processes are still simple and conventional. The quality the salted fish is affected by the quality of the raw materials and the amount and purity of salt. In addition, the process of breakdown proteins by enzymes and the activity of bacteria can reduce the organoleptic scores of fish which in turn results in development of off odor in the fish (Yuliati et al., 2021). In this case, the protein content of African catfish is higher than that of Tilapia resulting low scores of aroma in the sensory evaluation.

Figure 2.7.1.4. reports the results of sensorial evaluation of smoked fish. The mean scores for the sensory attributes of the smoked fish were highest in African catfish for the first two weeks. This was followed by *Barbus altanialis* with regards to test, aroma and overall acceptability. However, after the two weeks of storage, *Barbus* was already infested with moulds and could not be included for further sensory evaluation due safety concerns for consumption.

Figure 2.7.1.4. Mean scores for appearance, taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptability of smoked fish

After 4 weeks of storage, African catfish was no longer fit and acceptable for consumption with judgement from the visual appearance and odor. Therefore, there was no need to further include it in the sensory tests by panelists. The summary of the results is illustrated by the graphical figures below. This similar observation was noted for African catfish in the fourth sample evaluation point. However, Tilapia remained shelf stable and fit for the sensory evaluation all throughout the eight weeks of storage.

Figure 2.7.1.5. reports the results of sensorial evaluation of solar dried fish. Out of the 2 fish species that were solar dried, Tilapia had the highest mean scores compared to African catfish for all the sensory attributes. The mean scores for the African catfish were below the mean value of 4.

Figure 2.7.1.5. Mean scores for appearance, taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptability of solar dried fish

Additionally, all throughout the storage period, African catfish had lower mean values for the different sensory attributes compared to Tilapia.

Fish powder

The micronutrient composition of fish powder is reported in Table 2.7.1.3. The developed fish powder was rich in calcium, iron and zinc with amounts significantly above the recommended minimum, as indicated in a similar product, powdered Silver cyprinid (US 780:2012).

Product	g/100g (%)		mg/kg (ppm)		
	P	Ca	Fe	Zn	Se
Fish powder from carcasses	9.31±1.5	17.4±2.8	*	*	*

Values are means ± standard deviation of three determinations (n=3).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

As reported in D2.5, legumes are the main protein source in Ugandan diets, with animal source protein consumption being low. Fish is primarily recognised as a good source of protein in the diet. The fish species, namely Tilapia, Catfish and Barbu showed protein content within the reported range according to FAO food composition tables for Africa. In addition, dehydrated fish products such as the solar dried and smoked from the aforementioned species contain at least 46% protein (FAO 1968). This is important to curtail undernutrition especially among children under five years including wasting, stunting and underweight quoted at 4%, 29% and 11% respectively. According to the dietary guidelines developed in D2.6, fish is an important source of protein, healthy lipids and micronutrients. The guidelines recommend 2 – 3 servings (2–7 - 340 g) of different fish types per week.

However, fish is highly perishable and may not be easily accessible to consumers. Nonetheless, smoking, drying and salting represent low-cost preservation methods that rely on the dehydration principle. The shelf-life assessments showed that Nile Tilapia products had a longer shelf-life compared to African catfish. Smoking and salting were effective for shelf-life extension of Tilapia. Overall, the shelf life of the dried and smoked fish products was extended between 4 to 8 weeks at ambient conditions. Therefore, this increases their availability to consumers thus enhancing food and nutrition security.

As reported in D2.5, as Ugandan diets are mainly plant based, the mean intake of micronutrients such as zinc and Vitamin A remains below the recommended level. In addition, 35.8% and 50-53% of children under 5 suffer from Vitamin A deficiency and Iron-deficiency anaemia. The developed fish powder is rich in Zinc and Iron could help to enrich the diets of the consumers with these essential micronutrients.

4. References

- AOAC. (2005). Official methods of analysis, 18th ed. Association of Official Analytical Chemists
- FAO (1968). Food composition table for use in Africa
- FoodLAND (2024). Report D2.5. Dataset on chemico-physical characteristics of relevant food raw materials, ingredients and food products currently entering into the dietary patterns of different groups of consumers
- FoodLAND (2024). Report D2.6. Nutritional recommendations

2.7.2. Oils from new local varieties/species: fish oil (prototype n. 18)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The *Barbus altianalis* (Rippon Babel) is a native carp locally known as Kisinjja in Uganda. It is regarded as a high value species because it is cherished as culturally socially and economically important by communities in central and western regions of the country. The fish is also liked for its fatty soup. There has been successful effort to breed the fish in confinement (Rutaisire et al., 2005; Aruho et al., 2018) however, these could not meet the expected quality and demand for fingerlings for grow outs. Under this project, work has progressed to improve the spawning and Larvae weaning protocols (Deliverable 4.12) focused on increasing availability for the fish to be upscaled. In the study and validation activities samples were picked twice from landing site at the Forest beach at the river Nile and from one farm in central Uganda. Few farms with *B. altianalis* have fish with quite a lot of fat for processing because the fish of less than a kilo has no much fat. Fish picked from the wild had more fat for processing. The fat was largely obtained from the viscera of the fish. At the landing sites, the viscera are removed and made ready for transportation to the market. The fatty viscera are largely obtained from the fish that is starting the breeding stages where eggs require a lot of fat to build the eggs with vitellogenesis (Developing gonadal stages).

2. Results

Physical Properties of *Barbus altianalis* oil

The laboratory analysis was conducted to determine the physical properties of the sample, including specific gravity, refractive index, viscosity, and melting point. The results are reported in Table 2.7.2.1. The specific gravity of the sample averages at 0.9207, indicating the relative density compared to water. The values are consistent across the samples, with minimal variation, which is typical for uniform oil samples. The refractive index of the sample averages at 1.4873, which is within the expected range for fish oils, indicating the purity and quality of the sample. The average viscosity is 20.67 cP. This value is typical for fish oil, reflecting its resistance to flow at a specified temperature. The slight variation between samples was due to minor differences in temperature during measurement or sample composition. The melting point is consistently measured at -5°C across all samples, which is characteristic of fish oil. This consistency indicates that the samples are stable and have a similar fatty acid composition.

Table 2.7.2.1. Showing the analysis of the physical parameters of the *Barbus altianalis* oil fat

Sample No.	Specific Gravity	Reflective index	Viscosity (cP)	Melting point (°C)
1	0.921	*	*	*
2	0.922	*	*	*

3	0.919	*	*	*
Average	0.9207	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Chemical analysis

Table 2.7.2.2. shows the results of the chemical analysis carried out on the *Barbus altianalis* oils, that were compared against the Codex Alimentarius standard for fish oil (CXS 329-2017), which outlines acceptable limits for key quality indicators such as acid value, peroxide value, and anisidine value. For twice the analysis was done, the anisidine value was within the acceptable range, indicating that secondary oxidation products (aldehydes) are within safe limits. This suggests that the oil has not undergone extensive secondary oxidation, which is a positive sign regarding its freshness and stability. However, the acid value still exceeded the Codex standard although showing some improvement in the validated sample. Relatively high acid value indicates the presence of free fatty acids, which may result from hydrolysis due to prolonged or improper storage conditions. This can also be a sign of poor raw material quality or degradation during processing. The iodine value provides an indication of the degree of unsaturation of the fatty acids in the oil. While the Codex standard does not specify an iodine value for fish oil, the result suggests a moderate level of unsaturation, which is typical for fish oils. The moisture content was notably still high in both analyses. While not directly addressed by the Codex standard, high moisture content in oil is undesirable as it can promote microbial growth and accelerate the degradation of the oil through hydrolytic rancidity. The saponifiable matter is within expected ranges for fish oils, indicating the presence of fatty acids that can undergo saponification. This is a positive indicator of oil quality, though it is not directly regulated by Codex. The unsaponifiable matter was still relatively higher than typically expected, indicating still some presence of non-lipid components such as sterols, hydrocarbons, and other impurities. This could affect the purity and quality of the oil.

Measures to improve the purity and stability are implemented by reducing oxidation process through proper storage e.g., using packaging materials that offer better protection against oxygen and light, such as opaque and airtight containers and add natural or synthetic antioxidants to the oil to slow down the oxidation process. To avoid moisture, the oil should be stored in a dry environment and use moisture-barrier packaging to prevent moisture absorption during storage.

Table 2.7.2.2. Chemical parameters of *Barbus altianalis* oils

Chemical Parameter	Results during experimentation	Results 2 during validation	Codex Standard (CXS 329-2017)
Acid Value (mg KOH/g)	10.367	11	≤ 3 mg KOH/g

Chemical Parameter	Results during experimentation	Results 2 during validation	Codex Standard (CXS 329-2017)
Anisidine Value (% mass/mass)	*	*	*
Iodine Value (I ₂ /100g)	*	*	*
Moisture Content (% mass/mass)	*	*	*
Peroxide Value (meq/kg)	*	*	*
Saponifiable Matter (mg KOH/g)	*	*	*
Unsaponifiable Matter (% mass/mass)	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

The two analyses conducted (based on Codex standard scale) indicated that the oils were relatively improved and only needed small further refinement. These studies under this project were crucial as a basis for continuous stabilisation of the oils. The fact that also these are extracted from fish offal's, they could be incidentally mixed with other type of waste and other unpalatable substances, there is need to continuously improve the quality of oil. Some communities eat these offals directly (personal communication with fishers); this however, means that the safety of consumers can only be assured through production of quality oil from the fatty viscera.

The oils contain large amount of omega 6 fatty acids which are a type of polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA), that supports brain growth, help stimulate skin and hair growth, maintain bone health, regulate metabolism, and maintain the reproductive system. Hence processing the oils is a critical path to ensure access to useful fatty acids cheaply for children and women. Like other animal fats, the oils could be regularly consumed through other sources, such as mixing the oil directly in prepared ready bean and pea nut sauces, as is a practice by many communities, including spoon full of cow gee in prepared ready bean sauce, referred to as 'appetizer'. The challenge is that, compared to the source and Nile perch, the oils from the offal's of *Barbus altianalis* do not represent a significant quantity to processes, but could be significant if obtained from all the fish waste.

The post project recommendation is to define and determine oil extraction protocols from all the fish species offals, since they could be easily obtained from fish factories and from landing sites. Fish and fish products are some of the products that have been highly recommended for increased consumption by all age groups largely, children and youth (deliverable 2.6).

4. References

The Codex Alimentarius standard for fish oil (CXS 329-2017), Adopted in 2017. Amended in 2021. Editorial correction in 2023.

Aruho, C., Walakira, J. K., & Rutaisire, J. (2018). An overview of domestication potential of *Barbus altianalis* (Boulenger, 1900) in Uganda. *Aquaculture reports*, 11, 31-37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aqrep.2018.05.001>

2.7.3. Snacks from new local varieties/species: fish cakes and crackers (prototype n. 22)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Traditionally, the most common preservation methods are smoking, drying and salting. However, secondary fish products such as fish balls, fish crackers and fish nuggets provide higher value and can be processed from raw materials such as mince from fish carcasses. Also extruded (squeezed through heating process) ready to eat snacks can be processed using micronutrient dense fish bone powder as a base. These products were developed from farmed fish species of Tilapia, Barbus, Catfish and Labeo sp by the research team from National Agricultural Research Laboratories (NARL) an institute of National Agricultural Research Organisation (NARO). The processing technologies used to develop the products included deep frying (battered & breaded products – fish balls, nuggets and crackers) and extrusion – fish bone-maize snack. Innovative processing of fish by-products for shelf stability, convenient and nutritious secondary products can benefit fish farmers, SMEs (processors/traders) and fish consumers. The range of products include: fish crackers, nuggets, burgers, smoked fillets, balls, extruded snacks, fingers, cakes. Products were developed from fish fillets, mince and carcasses.

2. Results

Table 2.7.3.1. Proximate composition of fish products

Products/Nutrient composition (%)	Crude Protein	Crude Fat	Dry Matter Content	Ash
Soft smoked fish fillets	79.4±0.2	*	*	*
Fish snacks (extruded)	11.9±0.1	*	*	*
Fish fingers	36.6±0.2	*	*	*
Fish nuggets	15.3±0.8	*	*	*

Fish balls	14.3±0.2	*	*	*
Fish cakes	20.2±0.2	*	*	*
Fish crackers	14.9±0.4	*	*	*
Fish burgers	17.2±0.4	*	*	*

Values are means ± standard deviation of three determinations (n=3).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.7.3.1. reports the proximate composition of the developed fish products. In the analysed samples, the soft smoked fish fillet had the highest protein content (approximately 80%) while the extruded fish snacks showed the lowest (approximately 12%). For crude fat, the highest value was recorded for the fish fingers (28.7%) and lowest in extruded fish snacks (5.5%). Dry matter content was highest in extruded fish snack 97.4% and lowest in the fish nuggets (53.1%). Ash content was highest in extruded fish snack (5.1%) and lowest in the fish cakes (1.7%).

Sensory evaluation during validation

During the validation step, the developed fish products (fish balls, fish cakes, fish fingers, fish nuggets, extruded fish bone snacks) were evaluated by the trainees for the different sensory attributes including appearance, taste, texture, aroma and overall acceptability on a 9 point hedonic scale. Results from the sensory evaluation are reported in Figure 2.7.3.1 and indicate that all product were considered highly acceptable and fish nuggets were the most acceptable ones.

Figure 2.7.3.1. Sensory evaluation of the products during the validation exercise

3. Conclusions

The developed snacks are rich in protein and micronutrients, which are important against undernutrition and hidden hunger especially among children under 5 years. Children are often given snacks in between meals. The developed innovative fish products are convenient nutrient dense snacks that have the potential to substitute low nutritional value snacks. Improved snacking patterns among children have been shown to improve their nutrition (Kabahenda et al., 2011). It is envisaged that incorporating nutrient dense snacks in the diets of children will improve their overall nutrition and health.

4. References

Kabahenda, M., Mullis, R. M., Nickols, S. Y., & Erhardt, J. G. (2011). Nutrition education to improve dietary intake and micronutrient nutriture among children in less-resourced areas: a randomised controlled intervention in Kabarole district, western Uganda. *South African Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 24(2), 83-88.

2.7.4. Other products from new local varieties/species: other fish products (prototype n. 25a)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Solid fish hydrolysate as feed was produced from the fish offal/guts by lacto-fermentation (using Lactic Acid Bacteria – LAB).

2. Results

Composition of feed from fermented fish offals

The results of proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal are indicated in Table 2.7.4.1.

Table 2.7.4.1. Proximate and micronutrient composition of feed from fermented fish offal

Composition (% unless stated)	Feed from fermented fish offal	East African Standard spec (compounded poultry feed)
Moisture content	16.19±1.52	13
Total Ash	5.31±0.18	
Crude Protein	*	*
Crude Fibre	*	*

Crude Fat	*	*
Energy, Kcal/Kg	*	*
Ca	*	*
P	*	*

Values are means \pm standard deviation of three determinations (n=3).

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

3. Conclusions

The developed feed met the standard specification of a compounded poultry feed in terms of crude protein and phosphorus. Other attributes were marginally outside recommended range. Therefore, it is recommended that the feed should be improved to meet these criteria.

4. References

EAS (2023). EAS 90: Compounded poultry feed — Specification

2.8. ENAM

2.8.1. Oils from new local varieties/species: virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil (prototype n. 17)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The ingredients used for the production of a flavoured olive oil by using ginger powder were high-quality Picholine olives and ginger powder. The process begins with the olive fruits harvest when the ripeness index is measured at 3.5. To ensure optimal freshness and quality, the olives are processed within 24 hours of harvest. After harvesting, the ginger, which originates from India, is previously dried, crushed and ground into a uniform powder to preserve its aromatic and functional properties. The ginger powder is added to the olive oil in the malaxing phase, to the following concentrations: 0%, 1%, 1.5% and 2% (w/w). The malaxing process is carried out in a two-phase decanter, with the exact time-temperature conditions set at 45 minutes at about 27°C. Once the oil is produced, it undergoes centrifugation to separate the oil from the water and reduce the amount of ginger residue. Following centrifugation, a filtration step is conducted on a laboratory scale to eliminate any remaining ginger particles, resulting in a clearer olive oil (At industrial scale was carried out a static decantation phase allowing second clarification (natural

settling). because in Moroccan market (consumer), generally, the oil olive is preferred without supplement clarification (filtration)).

For packaging and storage, aliquots of the flavored olive oil are bottled under two different conditions: one at freezing temperatures (-18°C) and the other at room temperature.

For each concentration (0%, 1%, 1.5%, and 2%), a total of eight pairs of 250 ml bottles were prepared, with samples collected at various time points: T₀ (freshly produced in December 2023), T₁ (3 months, end of February 2024), T₂ (6 months, end of May 2024), and T₃ (9 months, end of August 2024) to evaluate their quality and functional properties.

The quality assessment involved determining the free acidity (expressed as percentage of oleic acid (%)), the peroxide value measured in milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram of oil (meq O₂/kg), and the K₂₃₂ and K₂₇₀ extinction coefficients calculated from absorbance at 232 and 270 nm, respectively, were measured in accordance with the European Official Methods described in the European Union Standard Methods Regulations 2568/91 and the subsequent amendments (EC, European Community Commission, 1991). All parameters were determined in triplicate for each sample.

2. Results

The results of the physico-chemical analysis of the samples studied are reported in Table 2.8.8.1. As can be noted, before storage, the samples showed quite similar values in terms of free acidity (between 0.22 and 0.23% for fresh olive oil and ginger-enriched oils, respectively), peroxide value (between 2.62 and 3.25 for oils enriched with 1.5% and for fresh olive oil, respectively), total phenols content (varying between 283 and 289 mg GAE/kg for 1% and 2% enriched oils, respectively) and coefficients K₂₃₂ (varying between 1.12 and 1.52 for 0.2% and fresh olive oil respectively) and K₂₇₂ (varying between 0.08 and 0.15 for 2% ginger-enriched oils and fresh olive oil, respectively).

Table 2.8.1.1. Physicochemical parameters of the fresh olive oil and the samples enriched with ginger (Flavoured Olive Oil FOO) at different concentrations for different storage periods

Sample	Free acidity (%)				Peroxide value (meq O ₂ /kg)			
	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Fresh olive oil	0.22±0.01aA	*	*	0.62±0.01aC	3.25±0.11aA	*	*	5.12±0.14aC
FOO-1.0%	0.23±0.01aA	*	*	0.37±0.01bB	2.89±0.04bA	*	*	3.85±0.10bC
FOO-1.5%	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FOO-2.0%	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
	K232				K272			

	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Fresh olive oil	1.52±0.02aA	*	*	1.74±0.01aB	0.15±0.01aA	*	*	0.19±0.02aB
FOO-1.0%	1.18±0.01bA	*	*	1.35±0.01bB	0.09±0.00bA	*	*	0.13±0.02bB
FOO-1.5%	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*
FOO-2.0%	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*

Total phenols content (mg GAE/kg)				
	T ₀	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃
Fresh olive oil	285±7aA	*	*	212±4aB
FOO-1.0%	283±10aA	*	*	245±7bB
FOO-1.5%	*	*	*	*
FOO-2.0%	*	*	*	*

Distinct capital letters represent significant differences between the same type of olive oil sample at different storage time, while different lower-case letters show significant differences between fresh olive oils and ginger-enriched olive oils at the same storage period ($p < 0.05$).

** Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]*

Although the samples induced quite the same physicochemical quality, it can be noted that the addition of ginger in different proportions was found to be responsible for preserving the physicochemical quality of olive oil. In fact, the samples enriched with ginger were associated with a slower deterioration of the physico-chemical quality indices studied compared to fresh oils. In the case of total phenols, the addition of ginger was found to be associated with a slower degradation of phenolic compounds. This process may also lead to the production of phenolic derivatives during storage, different from those obtained in the case of fresh olive oil. This can be further confirmed by a detailed analysis of the phenolic profiles of the samples studied.

3. Conclusions

No significant differences were evidenced after 3 months of storage of the oils at room temperature (T₀ vs T₃). Therefore, the oxidative stability of the obtained oil was guaranteed. Besides the positive effects on health by improving the quality of olive oil in general, this prototype is anticipated to improve the diversity of olive oil products on offer by flavouring and stimulating market demand for these specific products.

2.9. NUT

2.9.1. Other products: bean sauce (prototype n. 25b)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

The bean sauce is a product processed from dry common beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). Specifically, NARO Bean 1, a breeder-certified dry bean variety in Uganda, characterized by its large-sized seeds with white and dark blue stripes. This variety was selected because of its desirable characteristics including: early maturity of 60 to 68 days; high yield of 600 to 800 kg per acre (1500 – 200 kg/Ha); high zinc (31.4 – 34.2 ppm) and iron (65.8 – 72 ppm) contents) (MAIIF, 2019) and high sensory acceptability. The dry beans were delivered to Nutreal Limited by National Agricultural Research Organisation (NARO) supported farmers in Rakai District in Uganda. The beans were processed as described by Nattabirwa et al. (2018), with modifications. Briefly, the beans were sifted and sorted on a wire mesh to remove chuff, broken and shrivelled grain. The sorted beans were washed thrice with potable tap water and dried on wire mesh racks in a solar tent drier, until they attained a moisture content of 11-12%. The dry beans were milled using a commercial mill (Model YZMF, Yize, Shuliy Henan, China) with a 1.5 mm sieve and the flour was stored in plastic bags at room temperature (23 - 27 °C). The bean flour was extruded as described by Akande et al. (2017). Briefly, the bean flour was conditioned to a moisture content of 20% and thoroughly mixed using a stainless steel mixer for 15 min. The conditioned flour was then extruded using a DP70-III double screw inflating food machine (Jinan Eagle Machine Co. Ltd., Jinan, China). The extruder conditions were: feeding frequency of 30 Hz, cutting frequency of 50 Hz, and barrel temperatures of 60° C, 130° C, and 150° C in first, second, and third zones, respectively. After extrusion, the samples were cooled to room temperature under natural convection conditions. The samples were then milled into flour using a 30 B-C milling machine (Changzhou Erbang Drying Equipment Co. Ltd., China), packed in 225 mm * 40 mic BOPP bags, a label was attached and the product was and stored at ambient conditions until further use.

Bean sauce was prepared using a recipe previously developed by Nutreal Limited and as described on the label. Briefly: 1 finely chopped large onion was sautéed in 2 tablespoons of cooking oil; 2 finely chopped tomatoes were added and cooked; 2 heaped table spoons of bean flour were added and stirred; 500 ml of hot water was added slowly while stirring; salt and seasonings were added to taste and the sauce was simmered for 10 minutes before serving. The recipe as well as the ingredients and fuel were provided to the street vendors and they practiced preparing the bean sauce, in advance. A total of 302 street food vendors and their customers in Kampala district were interviewed after testing bean sauce. Street vendors were selected as the target users because they commonly serve cooked bean stew with chapatti to their clients. The stew is cooked using dry beans, which take 1-3 ours to cook, an inconvenient and costly process. The evaluation was conducted in the three busiest divisions of Kampala district namely: Kawempe (which includes the kalerwe food Hub of the Foodland project), Nakawa and Rubaga. A tool below was developed and translated into Luganda (a commonly spoken language in central Uganda including Kampala), to ensure comprehension and used for data collection.

Tool for the evaluation of bean sauce among 302 street food vendors and their customers

We are conducting a study to evaluate the acceptability of a newly developed, fast-cooking bean sauce. The results will further steps to introduce the bean flour for preparing the sauce, to the street vendor market segment and surrounding retail shops.

Do you consent to participate in the study? YesNo.....

Instructions: You are provided with bean sauce. Please taste it and indicate how much you like or dislike it, using the scale provided below. Write the score/number that best reflects your feelings about the bean sauce and fish sauce, in the spaces provided.

Acceptability Scale (Ebipimo)	ATTRIBUTE (EKISANYIIZO)	SCORE (UBOBONERO)
1. Dislike very much (Sizagalira ddala)	Appearance (Endabika)	
2. Dislike moderately (Sizagala)	Color (Langi)	
3. Neither like nor dislike (wakati awo)	Aroma (Akawoowo)	
4. Like moderately (Nzagala)	Mouthfeel (Empulikika mu kamwa)	
5. Like very much (Nzagala nnyo)	Taste (Empooma)	
	After taste (Bwowulira mu kamwang'omazeokulya)	
	Overall acceptability (Okutwaalizaawamu)	

Date:Location:.....

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME & PARTICIPATION!

2. Results

Figure 2.9.1.1 Sensory Acceptability for the bean sauce among 303 street food vendors and their customers in Kampala District of Uganda

Figure 2.9.1.1 shows the sensory Acceptability for the bean sauce among 303 street food vendors and their customers in Kampala District of Uganda. The color of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by a combined 94% the respondents. Only 5% of the respondents were undecided and only 1% said that they did not like the colour. Similarly, the aroma of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 91.1%. Only 5% of the respondents were undecided and only 4% indicated that they did not like the aroma of the product. The thickness of the bean sauce was liked by all the respondents. The taste of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 87.5%. Only 6.6% were undecided and only 6% indicated that they did not like the taste. The aftertaste of bean sauce was also liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 90.7%. Only 5.6% were undecided and only 3.7% indicated that they did not like the aftertaste of the sauce. Unsurprisingly, overall the bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the majority of respondents resulting in a combined like score of 85.8%. Only 9.2% neither liked nor disliked the product and only 5% indicated that they did not like the product.

3. Conclusions

While beans are highly nutritious and commonly consumed in Uganda, their contribution to improving dietary nutrient intake and to reducing the high levels of malnutrition cited in D2.5 is

limited by a number of factors including high levels of antinutrients; poor quality and long cooking times of 1-4 hours (Nyakuni et al., 2008; Balamaze et al., 2008). This makes bean preparation laborious, with high fuel requirements. Availability and use of value-added products with reduced cooking times, such as the bean sauce developed and evaluated by Nutreal has the potential to increase bean consumption and contributing to high dietary macro and micronutrients. The extrusion cooking processing used enhances digestibility and nutritional value by increasing protein digestibility and reducing phytates and polyphenols that limit iron and zinc uptake (Nkundabombi et al., 2015; Ndagire et al., 2015; Nakitto et al., 2015). The bean sauce can therefore contribute to the nutritional recommendations developed for Uganda under the FoodLAND project (D2.6).

4. References

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2.9.2. Other products: amaranth-enriched wheat (prototype n. 25c)

1. New food raw materials, ingredients and products

Foods such as chapatti, mandazi, doughnuts, daddies and cakes are commonly sold by road side food vendors and consumed by many low income earners and youths in Uganda. The foods are made using mostly imported and highly white wheat flour. Locally grown grain amaranth (GA) (*Amaranthus cruentus*) is a suitable complement to wheat as it is locally grown, fast growing, draught resistant and nutritious. GA has 15% protein that is highly digestible and with a well-balanced amino acid profile as well as high levels of minerals and vitamins (Muyonga et al., 2008). Previously developed formulations of GA-wheat composite flour were further refined and evaluated for use in chapatti, a food that is commonly prepared and sold by street food vendors in Uganda. Composites with 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60% and 70% GA flour were formulated and their nutritional composition was calculated based on existing nutrient data. The flours were then used for making chapattis (savory flat breads). The chapatti were screened by 9 experienced evaluators (6 males and 3 females), for their sensory acceptability. The most acceptable composite was then evaluated among the street food vendors, concerning its potential for sale and use alongside and/or instead of pure wheat:

- Both Nutreal staff and street vendors assessed workability of the GA-wheat flour. The sensory acceptability of the chapattis made using from amaranth-wheat were also assessed by a total of 302 the street vendors and their customers who came to the stalls. Since chapattis are often served with the ordinary bean sauce, sensory acceptability of the combination of the chapattis and the Nutreal bean sauce was also assessed. The following 5-point hedonic scale was used for all sensory assessments: 1 = dislike very much; 2 = dislike slightly; 3 = neither like nor dislike; 4 = like slightly; 5 = like very much.

Note: The tools were translated into Luganda to enhance comprehension by respondents.

Tools for evaluation of amaranth-wheat flour by key stakeholders

Part 1: Tool for evaluation of workability of GA-wheat composite flour by street vendors

We are conducting a study to evaluate the acceptability of a newly developed, amaranth-enriched wheat flour. The results will further steps to introduce the flour for use by street food vendors for making chapattis.

Do you consent to participate in the study? YesNo.....

Instructions: You are provided with wheat flour enriched with amaranth flour. Please use it and tell us your experience and views about it, compared to the usual wheat flour.

1. How much water did you use?
2. How did the water you used compare to what you usually use for the normal wheat flour?
Select a response: 1: less 2: the same 3: more
3. How long did it take knead the dough?
4. How did the time it took compare to what you usually use for the normal wheat flour?
Select a response: 1 less 2: the same 3: more
5. Is the new type of dough easy to shape?
Select a response: 1 = shapes easily 2 = slightly hard 3 = Hard
6. How easy is it to shape compared to the normal wheat flour?
Select a response 1: Easier 2: the same 3: more difficult
7. Would you be willing to pay more if the you know that the flour is nutritious? 1. Yes...2. No
8. If yes how much per 2 kg pack
9. How much do you usually pay for the wheat flour you use? Select

1	2	3	4	5	6
3000	3500	4000	4500	5000	More than 5000

10. How many chapattis did you get out of the 2 kg of the new flour you were given?
11. How many chapattis do you get from a 2 kg pack from the flour you usually use?
12. Would you be willing to switch to using amaranth enriched wheat flour? 1. Yes 2. No

Part 2: Sensory evaluation of the chapattis

Instructions: You are provided with two samples of chapattis. One is make with amaranth wheat and the other made with the usual wheat flour. Please taste both and indicate how much you like or dislike them, using the scale provided below. Write the score/number that best reflects your feelings about the chapattis, in the spaces provided.

Acceptability Scale (Ebipimo)	ATTRIBUTE (EKISANYIIZO)	SCORE (UBOBONERO)
1. Dislike very much (Sizagalira ddala)	Appearance (Endabika)	
2. Dislike moderately (Sizagala)	Color (Langi)	
3. Neither like nor dislike (wakati awo)	Aroma (Akawoowo)	
4. Like moderately (Nzagala)	Mouthfeel (Empulikika mukamwa)	
5. Like very much (Nzagala nnyo)	Taste (Empooma)	
	After taste (Bwowulira mu kamwang'omazeokulya)	
	Overall acceptability (Okutwaalizaawamu)	

THANK YOU FOR YOUR TIME & PARTICIPATION!

2. Results

Table 2.9.2.1 Calculated protein (%) and contributions of the GA-wheat formulations to the % RDIs of nutrients of public health significance in Uganda

NUTRIENT	GA incorporation rates				
	10%	15%	20%	25%	30%
Protein (%)	*	*	*	*	*
% Contribution to RDIs of adults /100 g					
Energy	16.9	17.0	17.1	17.1	17.2
Protein	*	*	*	*	*
Total fat	*	*	*	*	*
Carbohydrate	*	*	*	*	*
Dietary fiber	*	*	*	*	*
Iron	*	*	*	*	*
Zinc	*	*	*	*	*
Folic acid	*	*	*	*	*

*RDI is based on 2000 calorie intake

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

All formulations are protein source as at least 12 % of their energy values is provided by protein.

Table 2.9.2.1 reports the calculated protein (%) and contributions of the GA-wheat formulations to the % RDIs of nutrients of public health significance in Uganda. When Nutreal experts evaluated the suitability of the GA-enriched flours for making chapati, it was observed that as % GA flour increases, the quantity of water required for dough making as well as the proofing time and dough elasticity reduce. Conversely, kneading time required for the dough increases (Table 2.9.2.2). Workability of the dough was generally better for composite flours with lower % of amaranth. Doughs with 20% GA flour were preferred because they require less kneading and proofing time.

Table 2.9.2.2 Evaluation of amaranth-wheat formulations by Nutreal experts for characteristics of practical and commercial importance

Quantity of GA flour (%) in wheat	Water (%) added to dough	Dough kneading time (min)	Dough proofing time (min)	Relative dough elasticity	Yield (# of 50 g chapatti per 250 g of flour)

20	13.1	4	*	*	*
30	11.8	4	*	*	*
40	11.5	6	*	*	*
50	11.5	7	*	*	*
60	11.1	9	*	*	*
70	11.1	9	*	*	*

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.9.2.3 Sensory screening of chapattis made with grain amaranth-enriched wheat composites, evaluated by Nutreal experts using a 5-point hedonic scale

Attribute	Grain amaranth flour inclusion rate (%)					
	20	30	40	50	60	70
Appearance	*	*	*	*	*	*
Color	*	*	*	*	*	*
Aroma	*	*	*	*	*	*
Texture	*	*	*	*	*	*
Mouth feel	*	*	*	*	*	*
Taste	*	*	*	*	*	*
After taste	*	*	*	*	*	*
Overall acceptability	4.7±0.50 ^a	3.8±0.67 ^{ab}	3.7±0.71 ^b	3.0±1.22 ^{bc}	2.9±1.36 ^{bc}	2.6±1.33 ^c

* Full data set is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14944390> [Zenodo, DOI]

Table 2.92.3 reports the sensorial analysis results of chapattis made with grain amaranth-enriched wheat composites, evaluated by Nutreal experts using a 5-point hedonic scale.

Sensory acceptability of the chapattis reduced as amaranth levels increased. Chapattis with 20% amaranth had the highest overall acceptability score followed by those with 30% amaranth. While the attributes for 20% and 30% amaranth are not statistically different, when the 9 evaluators were further asked to select the best chapatti among those made with wheat enriched with 20, 40 and 70% GA, 7 (78%) of them selected the chapatti with 20%. When they were asked for the reason for their selection, they cited the good taste of the chapattis.

In order to test potential for the amaranth-wheat for commercial use the amaranth-wheat flour enriched with 20% GA was evaluated by 303 street food vendors engaged in making chapattis, on the same characteristics evaluated by Nutreal experts.

Results of evaluation of the ‘workability’ of amaranth-enriched wheat by Street food vendors

Figure 2.9.2.1 shows the performance of the amaranth enriched wheat for making chapatti compared to the usual white wheat. Most of the vendors (91.8%) reported that amaranth enriched

wheat flour was easy to use for making and shaping dough for chapattis. Only 8.2% reported that it was slightly harder to use. Compared to normal wheat, the vendors (90.2%) reported that amaranth enriched wheat flour was similar to pure wheat when it comes to ease of shaping.

Figure 2.9.2.1 Performance of the amaranth enriched wheat for making chapatti compared to the usual white wheat

The majority of vendors (88.5 and 90.2%) noted that there was no difference between amaranth enriched wheat flour and pure wheat flour regarding the time required to knead dough and the amount of water required. A small percentage (11.5%) reported that amaranth enriched wheat flour required less water compared to pure wheat and 9.8% reported that they spent more time kneading the amaranth-wheat dough (Figure above).

All the vendors produced at least more than 30 chapattis from 2 kg packs of amaranth enriched wheat flour. However, the majority (75.4%) reported that they usually make more chapattis when using pure wheat flour (Figure above). This could be due to the reduced elasticity of dough made using amaranth-wheat flour. Most of the vendors (73.8%) expressed willingness to use amaranth enriched wheat flour, however, most vendors (79.8%) were not willing to pay more for amaranth enriched wheat because they would not be able to make a profit from

their business and their consumers would not be willing to pay more for the chapattis. A small percentage (20.2%) was willing to pay more for the amaranth-wheat.

When the sensory acceptability of chapattis made from wheat flour with and without amaranth were evaluated by the 302 street food vendors and their customers, results (Figure below) indicated that chapattis made with amaranth enriched wheat were liked very much by majority of the respondents (62.9%) while the chapattis made with pure wheat were liked moderately by the majority of consumers. The most preferred attributes for amaranth-wheat chapattis were thickness (86.9%), color (70%) and taste (65.2%) while for the chapatti made with pure wheat were color (60.1%) and aroma (55.9%). Majority (58.1%) of the consumers liked the chapatti made with pure wheat moderately whereas only (25.6%) liked it very much (Figure 2.9.2.2). While the results indicate that the chapatti made with amaranth-wheat has higher sensory acceptability than those made from pure wheat, the two types of chapattis are appreciated for their different attributes.

Figure 2.9.2.2 Sensory acceptability of chapattis made with amaranth-wheat and those made with ordinary white wheat, to 302 street food vendors and their customers

3. Conclusions

The amaranth-enriched wheat and the chapattis made from it were both highly acceptable and nutrient-enhanced. Given the higher levels of protein compared to products made from pure wheat, they have potential to improve dietary protein intake and to reduce the high levels of malnutrition cited in D2.5. They are particularly suitable for addressing the problem of protein energy malnutrition, which is prevalent in Uganda. The amaranth-wheat can therefore contribute to the nutritional recommendations developed for Uganda under the FoodLAND project (D2.6). However, it is important to underline the need to determine mycotoxin content in cereals as critical aspect to ensure food safety.

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The views and opinions expressed in this document are the sole responsibility of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

3. General conclusions

A variety of innovative ingredients and food products, rich in nutrients and nutraceuticals, has been successfully developed and characterized. These new ingredients and foods have originated from local raw materials and varieties, with the aim of valorizing typical productions, and nutritionally enriched to address the nutritional gaps identified in report D2.5 and align with the dietary recommendations outlined in D2.6.

This deliverable contains the characterization of the optimized formulations validated at industrial level. The obtained ingredients and food products show improved performances, both in terms of techno-functional properties (e.g., shorter cooking or soaking time, higher water holding capacity or viscosity development) and of nutritional quality (high protein and fiber content, high bioactive compounds content and antioxidant activity), therefore show high potential for addressing FoodLAND goals of promoting dietary enrichment and food products diversification.

However, to reach those objectives, a wide adoption and implementation of the developed prototypes are necessary. Further analytical determinations should be carried out for some products (e.g., mycotoxins content in cereal-based products as food safety indicator, full aminoacidic profile and antinutritional compounds content in legume-based products for proper nutritional evaluation) before positioning them in the market. The consumers' acceptance should be evaluated and specific communication strategies put in place. For this aim, the engagement among the stakeholders should continue after the project ends.

